

SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY IN BRATISLAVA

Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology

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Electromagnetic and Electrothermal modeling of superconductors for large scale applications

Dissertation Thesis

Bratislava 2021

Anang Dadhich, MSc.

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Abstract

High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) stacks and bulks can trap high magnetic fields. These superconductors can be used in the rotor of fully superconducting electric motors for aviation, which are capable of reducing greenhouse emissions and noise levels by aircraft. It has been observed, though, that these superconducting samples are subjected to ripple fields, generated by the windings in the stator, that can rapidly demagnetize the HTS stacks and bulks. Thus, it is important to analyze this behavior of superconductors accurately because it is a major issue for applications like HTS motors and generators, where background ripple field amplitudes and frequencies are relatively high (often of the order of kHz).

Also, superconductors are vulnerable to Electro-Thermal quench due to large screening currents or high voltages. This type of quench is required to be taken into account while designing applications with superconducting windings (motors or electro-magnets), but modeling the Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal behavior of the superconductors together in a commercial software is a time consuming and complicated affair. Thus, there is a need for a fast and accurate numerical software to model the overall function of full-scale magnets.

We have performed Electro-Magnetic modeling by means of our in-house 2D MEMEP (Minimum Electro-Magnetic Entropy Production) method, that takes the non-linear resistivity of superconductors, to show that the demagnetization of stacks depends on various cross field parameters and tape geometry. For this purpose, we have derived analytical formulas for the time constant to quickly calculate demagnetization of HTS tapes and stacks, as well. We have also developed a novel effective $E(J)$ relation, based on dynamic magneto-resistance, which we use in MEMEP method to simulate the demagnetization of superconducting stacks and bulks for millions of cycles of applied cross ripple field in relatively very short time, and for very thick stacks (up to 100 tapes). The results from dynamic magneto-resistance agree well with those from the conventional Power-Law relation, but are orders of magnitude faster. For high number of ripple field cycles, we have observed that the trapped field

reaches a permanent non-zero asymptotic value for HTS stacks, if the ripple field amplitude is lower than the tape's parallel penetration field. Using these models, we also discuss benefits of different configurations of superconductors, for the above mentioned problem, such as bulks, isolated stacks, and soldered stacks. We have found that, contrary than stated in previous works, bulks are more resilient to cross-fields than stacks.

We have also developed a novel and fast model in C++, which performs coupled Electro-Magnetic, and Electro-Thermal analysis, using the variational methods MEMEP and METEP (Minimum Electro-Thermal Entropy Production), respectively. The software is highly customizable and fast, and is able to accurately simulate the physics of Electro-Thermal quench of superconducting bulks in its current, initial stage of development.

The models developed during this thesis work can be used for a quick and complete Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal analysis of practical large scale superconducting applications such as high field magnets, fault current limiters, motors, and generators, by engineers and scientists.

Abstrakt

Stĺpce pások z vysokoteplotných supravodičov (HTS) (pásky sú položené na seba) a objemové supravodiče sú schopné zachytávať vysoké magnetické polia. Možno ich tak využiť v rotoroch plne supravodivých elektrických motorov pre letectvo, ktoré sú schopné znižovať emisie skleníkových plynov a hladinu hluku v lietadle. Pozorovaním sa zistilo, že v týchto aplikáciách sú vystavené zvládnutým priečnym poliam generovaným vinutiami v statore, ktoré môžu rýchlo demagnetizovať stĺpce supravodivých pások a objemové supravodiče. Je preto dôležité presne analyzovať takéto správanie sa supravodičov, pretože predstavuje hlavný problém aplikácií ako sú HTS motory a generátory, pri ktorých sú amplitúdy a frekvencie vonkajších priečných polí pomerne vysoké (často rádovo v kHz).

Supravodiče sú tiež ohrozené elektro-tepelným prechodom do normálneho stavu v dôsledku veľkých tieniacich prúdov alebo vysokého napätia. Tento typ prechodu do normálneho stavu je potrebné zohľadniť pri navrhovaní aplikácií so supravodivými vinutiami (motory alebo elektro-magnety), ale modelovanie elektromagnetického a elektro-tepelného správania sa supravodičov v komerčnom softvéri je časovo náročné a komplikované. Existuje teda potreba rýchleho a presného numerického softvéru na modelovanie celkovej funkcie magnetov v plnom rozsahu.

Vykonali sme elektromagnetické modelovanie pomocou vlastnej internej metódy 2D MEMEP (Minimum Electro-Magnetic Entropy Production), ktorá využíva nelineárny odpor supravodičov, aby sme preukázali, že demagnetizácia stĺpcov supravodivých pások, závisí od rôznych parametrov krížového poľa a od geometrie pásky. Za týmto účelom sme odvodili analytické vzorce pre časovú konštantu na rýchly výpočet demagnetizácie HTS pások a taktiež stĺpcov supravodivých pások. Vyvinuli sme tiež nový efektívny vzťah $E(J)$, založený na dynamickej magneto-rezistencii, ktorú používame v metóde MEMEP na simuláciu demagnetizácie stĺpcov supravodivých pások a objemových supravodičov pre milióny cyklov aplikovaného krížového poľa v relatívne veľmi krátkom čase a pre veľmi hrubé stĺpce (až 100 pások). Výsledky získané s využitím dynamickej magneto-rezistencie sa dobre zhodujú s výsledkami

založenými na konvenčnom “Power-Law” vzťahu, sú však rádovo rýchlejšie. Pri vysokom počte cyklov priečného poľa sme pozorovali, že zachytené pole dosahuje pre stĺpce supravodivých pásov permanentnú nenulovú asymptotickú hodnotu, ak je amplitúda poľa nižšia ako paralelné pole prieniku pásy. S využitím týchto modelov tiež skúmame výhody rôznych konfigurácií supravodičov pre vyššie uvedený problém, ako sú napríklad objemové supravodiče, stĺpce izolovaných supravodivých pásov a stĺpce spájkovaných pásov. Na rozdiel od predchádzajúcich prác sme zistili, že objemové supravodiče sú voči priečnym poliam odolnejšie ako stĺpce supravodivých pásov.

Vyvinuli sme tiež nový a rýchly model v jazyku C++, ktorý vykonáva kombinovanú elektromagnetickú a elektro-teplnú analýzu pomocou variačných metód MEMEP a METEP (Minimum Electro-Thermal Entropy Production). Tento softvér je vysoko prispôsobiteľný a rýchly a v súčasnej počiatočnej fáze vývoja umožňuje presne simulovať fyziku elektro-teplného prechodu objemových supravodičov do normálneho stavu.

Modely vyvinuté v priebehu tejto dizertačnej práce môžu inžinieri a vedci použiť na rýchlu a úplnú elektromagnetickú a elektro-teplnú analýzu praktických supravodivých aplikácií, ako sú magnety pre vysoké polia, obmedzovače skratových prúdov, motory a generátory.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

It was in ancient Greece where Thales (around 600 BC), and later Aristotle (around 300 BC), discovered static electricity by rubbing fur to amber, realizing a new type of attraction force. Archaeologists at sites in Baghdad and Rome too have dug up some clay pots with copper sheet linings inside it, which are speculated to be ancient batteries for generating light, proving that the fascination and usage of electricity has been around for a long time in the world history. But it was Benjamin Franklin in 1752 with his famous kite experiment, and Thomas Alva Edison in 1879 with his electric bulb invention, who unveiled this new form of energy in front of the world for practical usage. Today, electrical energy has changed the face of our planet by raising the standard of living, developing multifaceted technology in various sectors, and enabling scientists with advanced tools to conduct innovative research for driving the world into a brighter future.

The first practical electromagnet was invented in 1824 by the British scientist, William Sturgeon, who is also credited for inventing the first practical electric motor in 1832. This electromagnet was a simple apparatus, involving a horseshoe shaped iron core wrapped with non-insulated wire, and was able to support 4 kg of weight. Since then, the scientists and engineers have been able to develop very powerful electromagnets (conventional, up to 2 Tesla) and electric motors, which are widely used in various applications such as research, transportation, industry, and power generation and transmission. The global market for magnets reached a value of over US\$ 20.7 billion in 2020 [1], with a high growing demand to build powerful magnets (above 40 T), specially for applications like particle accelerators (CERN), fusion reactors (Tokamak, ITER), and high-field magnets in research institutions. Currently, approximately one third of world electricity is consumed by electrical machine industry [2], out of which around 70 percent energy is consumed by electric motors [3]. Electric motors, and the systems where they are used, holds top

rank for largest electricity end-use globally, with around 43-46 percent energy consumption around the world, and about 6 gigatonnes in CO₂ emissions [4]. With such a huge global usage and environmental impact, the needs of the society are getting difficult to be achieved using conventional technology, and it is essential and imperative to continue conducting research to make these electrical machines and electromagnets more powerful, efficient, green, and viable for public utilization.

Figure 1.1: Trend of discovery of major superconducting materials over the last century.

One way to fulfill the aforementioned requirements is to use superconducting materials in global electric applications. Superconducting machines (and motors) have shown to be more efficient over the decades with wider power-rating ranges, and the first attempt to replace the copper windings with Low Temperature Superconductors (LTS) in electrical machines was made in 1960s. The major benefit of this substitution was the reduction in size and weight of the system. Since the cryogenics were liquid Helium based, the cost and design complexities were huge, and the AC losses were too high in the armature windings, making only DC current feasible for such an experiment. With the discovery of High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) in 1980s (Figure 1.1), more materials were considered to be used at relatively higher temperatures (up to 77 K), which reduced the costs for cooling systems, and made these machines more efficient [5]. Superconducting motors and generators are considered now for applications where size and weight are the major requirements

(and which can be cooled by either liquid Nitrogen or advanced cryocoolers), such as wind turbines, electric aircraft propulsion, electric motors for ship propulsion etc. For superconducting machines, a high increase in torque and power density can also be achieved.

Similarly, High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) coils can be used in building extremely high field magnets, such as the 45.5 T DC magnet built by MagLab, which holds the current record of the world's most powerful magnet [6]. The major benefits of employing superconductors to fabricate such high field magnets are low power requirements, compactness, and very high winding current densities (MagLab's magnet is able to operate at 1260 A/mm² current density). Superconducting DC high-field magnets also provide operation cost reduction, emission savings, steady-state operation and lower maintenance, enabling more available hours per year of usage. However, since the superconductors work at very low temperatures, the cost of re Fridgeration of these materials still needs to be kept in mind, which has to be atleast above "break-even", i.e. not incurring capital losses as compared to the conventional electromagnetic systems. Latest furtherance in cryogenics and development of complex oxide high temperature superconducting materials do solve this problem to some extent.

1.1 Problem description and need

Electric aircraft

A recent interest that is growing for superconducting applications is in the civil aviation industry. Over 4.5 billion passengers were carried globally by airlines in 2019, which produced around 915 million tonnes of CO₂ worldwide. The CO₂ emission trend for aviation from International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO)- 2019 environmental report (Figure 1.2) shows that, even with conventional improvements in the aviation technologies, we are going to see a major hike in CO₂ emissions by 2050 [7], since commercial flight activities are expected to normally resume after the Covid pandemic. In fact, the airplanes are expected to generate about 43 gigatonnes of greenhouse particulates, like CO₂ and NO_x, by 2050, and may consume up to 5 percent of world's remaining carbon budget, if remained unchecked [8]. The increasing trends for NO_x emissions and noise levels by aircraft can also be seen in ICAO environmental report - 2019 [7]. The air traffic is predicted to grow by 5 percent every year, and, hence, these emissions are forecasted to be tripled by the mid century. Earth will still suffer around 2.7- 3.5 Celcius of temperature increase by the end of this century, even if greenhouse reduction measures are taken for all fossil fuel applications. International Energy Agency (IEA) forecasts that

1.1. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND NEED

Figure 1.2: CO₂ emissions trend for aircraft from year 2005 to 2050, with dashed line for low aircraft technology development scenario. Picture taken, with permission, from International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) Environmental report- 2019 [7].

there is a 50 percent chance of keeping the temperature rise below 2° Celcius, which will definitely be lost by 2040, if very aggressive carbon emission cuts are not being made [9]. Thus, keeping the global temperature levels under this limit has been a goal set by United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) under the Paris Agreement, obligating the aviation sector for playing its role in meeting this requirement.

The Europe’s Vision for Aviation, ACARE Flightpath 2050, aims to reduce CO₂ emissions by 75 percent, NO_x and particulate release by 90 percent, fuel burn by 70 percent, and noise by 65 percent(71 dB) generated by aircraft, as compared to the 2000 data for aviation [10]. Since the conventional upgrades in the fuselage and wing design, and jet propulsion, of aircraft are not sufficient to meet these targets, Distributed Propulsion (DP) systems, using the latest superconductor technology, are being highly considered for making significant changes in fuel efficiency, and directly reducing Carbon and Nitrogen emissions. NASA’s X-57 Maxwell, Aurora Flight Sciences’ XV-24 Lightning strike, Joby S2, and Airbus Vahana VTOL (Vertical Take-Off and Landing) are some of the proposed and developed aircraft employing this technology for both fixed wing and VTOL configuration aircraft [11]. A 1-5 MW superconducting motor or generator can be used in large aircraft (like Airbus

A-320) propulsion systems due to the high power levels. A hybrid type of the DP system, Hybrid Electric Distributed Propulsion (HDEP), is the one which uses conventional electric or superconducting motors in conjunction with jet fuels, which can be configured in two different architectures - Series HDEP and Parallel HDEP. In Series HDEP, electrical power is generated using an Internal Combustion Engine (ICE), and the battery power is delivered to the propulsor via electric buses. Contrastingly, Parallel HDEP has an option to run the ICE continuously and use the electric power to reduce fuel flow, or to disconnect the ICE (using a mechanical clutch) to operate the aircraft independently in fully-electric mode for some part of the flight envelope, such as during cruising and landing [12]. Some of the proposed upcoming hybrid electric aircraft, employing HDEP systems, are XTI Tri-Fan 600 (Series HDEP, 2024), Boeing SUGAR Volt (Parallel HDEP, 2035), and Airbus/Rolls-Royce E-Thrust (Series HDEP, 2050) [12]. For an aircraft, HDEP and DP systems improve the aerodynamics (by Aero-propulsive coupling), control (using DP based control), and electrical propulsive efficiency, and shrink noise levels, which can reduce the greenhouse emissions of an entire future aircraft system by up to 70 percent, thereby, enabling the aviation sector to achieve the high targets set by Flightpath 2050 [11, 13].

Superconducting stacks of tapes and bulks can be used as strong permanent magnets in fully superconducting motors for hybrid electric aircraft, as can be seen in Figure 2.8. For ASuMED project, where our institute participated, HTS stacks are used in the rotors of the HTS motor [14]. The major issue with such superconducting motors is the high rate of cross-field demagnetization of HTS tapes present in the rotor of the motor due to stray ripple magnetic fields from motor background/surroundings, as can be seen in Figure 1.3. This makes the superconductor lose its trapped field, and, hence, the magnetization, thus causing the premature stopping of motor. Some very important work has been done in this field, but a detailed analysis of this feature with a practical design perspective is still missing. The numerical analysis methods and commercial software used for the computation of electromagnetic state variables in this phenomenon are quite slow, and, thus, a better program to model the cross field demagnetization of superconductors is required. Also, the publications for the cross field demagnetization are only available for unrealistically thick tapes, and for very low number of tapes in a HTS stack (10 tapes) and applied magnetic field cycles (150-200 cycles), which are not enough to model a practical case of the superconducting motors in HDEP systems in hybrid electric aircraft, that requires calculations for millions of ripple field cycles [15–23]. Thus, there is a huge demand for a simple software that can analyze this phenomenon of cross field demagnetization of very thick and realistic HTS stacks for large number of applied field cycles.

Figure 1.3: The rotors and stator in a superconducting motor faces ripple fields from all directions, which leads to demagnetization of the superconducting magnets in the motor. Motor Design by Oswald Elektromotoren GmbH, and calculation by Dr. Francesco Grilli, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology [14].

High-field magnets and power industry

The discovery of High Temperature Superconductors and, previously, Low Temperature Superconductors has opened new avenues for the researchers to generate high magnetic field for research and commercial applications. Using superconductors to construct a high field magnet contributes towards energy and emissions savings. Additionally, superconducting power grid elements, such as transformers, generators, reactors, and cables contribute towards efficient generation and transmission of power.

One of the major problems that the superconducting coils in high field magnets and electrical applications face is the electro-magneto-thermal quench, which can drive the superconductor material into its ‘normal’ state, where all the benefits of superconductivity cease to exist [24, 25]. Even worse, electro-thermal quench can permanently damage the device. This can occur due to high applied currents, high intensity magnetic field environment, and/or localized temperature variations in the material due to the non-linear behavior of superconductors. However, in certain special devices like fault-current limiters and fault-current transformers, electro-thermal quench actually protects the grid from short-circuits and other faults in the network by drastically reducing the peak currents in the faulty event. In any case, it is essential to model the quench behavior in designing of superconducting magnets under different local electro-thermal conditions, as the quenching effect has the ability to rapidly destroy the superconducting magnets.

There are a large amount of software that can model the Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal behavior of superconductors, for electro-thermal quench and other phenomenon, but there is a need for a simple and fast software that can perform ‘coupled’ Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal analysis of superconductors quickly and accurately. This software could be scaled up to model full scale magnet and power applications.

1.2 Goals of PhD

1.2.1 Cross field demagnetization of superconducting stacks

The design of power applications like motors and generators require electro-magnetic modeling of highly non-linear eddy currents in superconductors, and the demagnetization process of the superconductor under the influence of external magnetic fields. It is the goal of this PhD to develop a 2D computer program, in C++, capable of modeling cross-field demagnetization in stacks

(a)

(b)

Figure 1.4: (a) Mockup of the hybrid superconducting ASuMED motor, presented at the Hannover Fair, 2019. (b) These types of HTS motors can be used in Hybrid Distributed Electric Propulsion (HDEP) for futuristic hybrid electric aircraft, as proposed by Airbus [14].

(of very wide and thin tapes), and bulks for realistic motors. Specifically, the detailed time constant analysis of different superconducting stacks and bulks, with its dependence on various electromagnetic state variables and design elements (thickness and width of HTS tapes, ripple field amplitude and frequency of the applied cross field, and number of tapes in a superconducting stack), will be performed. Semi-empirical formulas for demagnetization decay time constant are to be realized for HTS stacks of tapes. Results for the 2D numerical model, being developed using MEMEP method, are also required to be compared with 3D MEMEP method and analytical formulae results for benchmarking purposes.

It is also an aim of this PhD to develop an effective relation between electric field and current density of the superconductor using the dynamic magnetoresistance property of superconductors. As the superconducting motors for aviation operate at very high frequencies (in the range of 1000s of Hz), the 2D MEMEP model employing this effective relation should be able to calculate the demagnetization of very thick superconducting stacks (up to 100 tapes) for millions of cycles of applied cross field. The models developed will also be used to check demagnetization of novel creative stack configuration of soldered stacks. This work comes under the EU Horizon-2020 project, Advanced Superconducting Motor Experimental Demonstrator (ASuMED), where our goal is to develop a 1 MW fully superconducting motor demonstrator for hybrid electric aircraft, a mockup of which can be seen in Figure 1.4 (a). This motor can be used in HDEP systems for futuristic hybrid electric aircraft, as the one proposed by Airbus (Figure 1.4 (b)) [14].

1.2.2 Coupled Electro-Thermal modeling of superconductors

Local heat in a superconducting material is generated when the current density overcomes the critical current density, causing "thermal quench", thus, destroying the superconductivity of the material. This heat affects the electromagnetic properties of superconductors, which in turn affects the thermal properties of the superconductor. Another goal of the proposed thesis is to develop a simple and an effective software in C++, using original in-house methods (MEMEP and METEP), that can analyze this 'coupled' Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal behavior of superconductor under different inputs such as applied voltage and applied magnetic field. This software should be able to model the quench phenomenon of superconducting magnets accurately. Currently, in the initial stages of development, this program should be highly customizable to be able to consider other inputs, geometries, and analyses (like Mechanical) in future. This work comes under APVV-19-0536

1.2. GOALS OF PHD

project "High temperature superconducting coils in motors for electric and hybrid aircraft", and European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) project - High-Temperature Superconductivity for Accelerating the Energy Transition (Hi-SCALE), which recently started in October, 2020 [26, 27].

Chapter 2

Background

3 years after developing the technology to liquify Helium and techniques for refrigeration at very low temperatures, H. Kammerlingh Onnes discovered an unusual phenomenon at his laboratory at Leiden in 1911. He observed a sharp drop in the electrical resistance, to an absolute value of zero, for numerous metals like Mercury, Tin, and Lead (Figure 2.1). It was realized that this effect occurred at a specific characteristic value of the material called Critical Temperature, T_c .

For his work, Dr. Onnes was awarded with a Nobel prize in 1913, and this effect was termed as superconductivity. Since then, this phenomenon has been a major topic of discussion in the scientific community, and a fundamental understanding of this property of metals (disappearance of resistance at low temperatures) has been researched in great details by several groups around the globe.

Several experiments have been performed demonstrating this property of total disappearance of resistance in metals. One of such experiments, known as persistent current experiment, has shown that the currents flow in superconducting rings for over a year without any measurable decrease. Indeed, the field generated by such a ring is expected to persist for a minimum of 10^5 years (and can go to up to the age of universe), evidencing no or incredibly tiny resistance. And, thus, superconductors were also called as perfect conductors [29].

In 1933, another major property of superconductors was discovered by Meissner and Ochsenfeld [30], in which it was found that these materials, at certain conditions, expel magnetic field when cooled down below T_c , under constant applied magnetic fields. This is in contrast to perfect conductivity where the metal attempts to trap the flux in. Named as Meissner effect, it

Figure 2.1: Drop in resistivity of Mercury, as noted by K. Onnes [28].

showed that superconductivity can also be destroyed by another constraint, being the Critical Magnetic Field H_c . Later, it was realized that perfect diamagnetism is possible only for superconducting bulk samples as the field penetrates by a very small distance, which lies in the range of around 50 to 1000 nm, named as London penetration depth after F. and H. London brothers, the founders of London equations for superconductivity in 1935 [31]. Close to T_c , the temperature dependence of H_c follows

$$H_c(T) = H_0(T) \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_c}\right). \quad (2.1)$$

For the first type of superconductors that were discovered, they also lose superconductivity when the current density exceeds a certain critical value, J_c . Related to this, Figure 2.2 shows a characteristic curve for a superconductor, featuring the phase diagram with current density J , temperature T , and applied magnetic field H , and a superconductor can be characterized by the critical values of the above three parameters [32]. If J , T , or H is above their critical value (outside the 2D surface), the superconductor presents macroscopic resistance.

Figure 2.2: Superconductor phase diagram for type I superconductors, showing relative relationships between temperature, applied field, and current density. The material is superconductor below the shown surface [32].

2.1 Types of superconductors

2.1.1 Type I and Type II superconductors

There are various classifications of superconductors, one of them being Type I and Type II superconductors, based on how superconductivity breaks down or how the phase changes with the application of external magnetic field.

Type I superconductors were the first kind of superconductors to be discovered, being all superconductors obtained from Kammerlingh Onnes of type I. The materials that transit to normal state abruptly above the critical magnetic field, H_c , are known as Type I superconductors. They show Meissner effect below this critical field. They also sharply become normal when J is above a critical value, J_c . Basic pure elemental metals such as Aluminum, Mercury, Tin and Lead come under Type I superconductors. TaSi_2 [33], being a superconducting alloy, and SiC:B [34], a heavily doped Boride covalent superconductor, are also Type I. Some materials can be pushed into superconducting state by applying external pressure. For example, Phosphorous, on applying pressures of around 2.5 Mbar, becomes superconducting with T_c of around 14-22 K, one of the highest in the category of Type I superconductors [35].

Discovered experimentally by Rjabinin and Shubnikov in 1935, type II superconductors, however, respond differently to applied magnetic fields and

2.1. TYPES OF SUPERCONDUCTORS

Figure 2.3: Behavior of type I and type II superconductors under the influence of applied magnetic field.

have two critical fields, H_{c1} and H_{c2} , as compared to type I superconductors, which can be seen in Figure 2.3. They act the same as Type I superconductors below H_{c1} , and show Meissner effect. At H_{c1} , the external magnetic field starts penetrating the material gradually. In this range between H_{c1} and H_{c2} , the material is still a superconductor, with the particularity that they present vortices of current (see Section 2.4. After applying a high strength field, that crosses the H_{c2} field value, the material becomes normal.

H_{c2} is very high for some materials, thus making these materials very advanced and useful for technological electromagnets. Indeed, some of these materials can be drawn into superconducting wires that can be used in several magnet and power applications. For example, H_{c2} can be as high as 15 T for NbTi. For Nb₃Sn, this value is up to 24.5 T, which makes them a prominent choice for high magnetic field applications like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) machines. NbTi is the most used superconducting material because of its simple fabrication process and mechanical flexibility, whereas Nb₃Sn is brittle. For comparison, conventional permanent magnets can produce field of up to around 1.6-2 T. Some complex oxides such as Bi₄Sr₂CaCu₂O₁₁ (BSSCO), YBa₂Cu₃O₇ (YBCO), and REBa₂Cu₃O₇(REBCO), where RE stands for "rare earth metal", also fall under the type II category. YBCO is famous as the first material to show type II superconductivity above 77 K, or the boiling point of Nitrogen, making superconductors very practical to be used with today's technology. For REBCO tapes, the limits of applied field can be much higher with irreversibility field of around 120 T (another important parameter at which macroscopic resistance appears inspite of the fact that superconducting vortices still exist) [36] [37]. The theory of type II superconductivity by Abrikosov also received Nobel prize in Physics in 2003.

Type I and Type II can rigorously be classified by the ratio of the London

penetration depth (λ) to the coherence length parameter (ξ). The superconductors below the ratio range classify as Type I superconductors, whereas the ratio holders are known as Type II superconductors [29]. The relation is explained in detail in Section 2.4, and this ratio is as

$$\kappa = \frac{\lambda}{\xi}, \quad (2.2)$$

where, κ is known as the Ginsburg-Landau parameter [38].

2.1.2 Low and High Temperature superconductors

Superconductivity is destroyed when the temperature rises over the material's characteristic critical temperature T_c . Thus, another way to classify superconductors is on the basis of their critical temperatures, i.e., Low Temperature Superconductors and High Temperature Superconductors.

Initially, superconductivity was found only in metals and alloys. The critical transition temperature for these pure metals can be as low as 0.000325 K for Rhodium (Rh), to around 7.196 K for Lead (Pb). In alloys, NbTi and Nb₃Sn have critical temperatures of around 10 K and 18 K respectively. Liquid Helium is generally used for achieving such low temperatures. Additionally, low temperature superconducting thin films of about 5×10^{-7} cm were fabricated as early as 1938, which showed great promise in terms of modifications under ambient temperatures [39].

In 1986, Bednorz and Muller discovered a ceramic oxide with critical temperature 35 K, a whole 12 K above the previous materials, and, thus, opened a bright possibility of superconductors working on practical applications at relatively high temperatures than Low Temperature Superconductors. They are termed High Temperature Superconductors, for which Bednorz and Muller were awarded Nobel Prize in 1987 instantly. Critical temperatures for such materials can be as high as 135 K, and upper critical field, H_{c2} , for such materials can range up to 200 T. YBCO, one of the most used high temperature superconductor, has critical temperature of about 92 K, and the variations of this compound (REBCO - Rare Earth Barium Copper Oxide, where RE is usually Y, Gd or Sm) are proposed to be used as coated conductor tapes in many magnets or power applications. Similarly, Magnesium diboride (MgB₂), a compound with critical temperature of 39 K, has been recorded to have H_{c2} of around 52 T in thin films [40]. An additional advantage of MgB₂ is its relatively low cost, specially comparing to REBCO. Some other high temperature superconductors can be seen in Table 2.1 [41]. In addition, liquid Nitrogen is readily available and very cheap, which makes them more desirable over

2.1. TYPES OF SUPERCONDUCTORS

Family	Symbol	Maximum Tc (K)
$(\text{La}_{1-x}\text{M}_x)_2\text{CuO}_4^a$	La-214	39
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7^b$	Y-123	92
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_8$	Y-124	80
$\text{Bi}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_{2n+4}$	Bi-22(n-1)n	122
$\text{Tl}_2\text{Ba}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_{2n+4}$	Tl-22(n-1)n	128
$\text{HgBa}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_{2n+2}$	Hg-12(n-1)n	135

Table 2.1: Some High temperature superconducting Cuprates. a: M can be Sr or Ba. b: Y can be replaced by other rare -earth elements.

Low Temperature Superconductors, using expensive and hard-to-manage liquid Helium. Furthermore, cryocoolers, based on compression and expansion of gases, enable to achieve intermediate temperatures (usually 15 to 70 K) in a practical way, using only tiny amounts of Helium.

Thus, for practical classification, High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) are those with high critical temperature above 77 K, where liquid Nitrogen can be used, or with mild critical temperature above 20 K, where liquid Hydrogen can be used. Similarly, superconductors with low critical temperatures below 20 K, where liquid Helium is used, are termed as Low Temperature Superconductors (LTS). A plot of this classification, with the year they were discovered, can be seen in Figure 1.1.

One drawback of using superconductors practically is the requirement of low temperature surroundings for them to work. Even the High Temperature Superconductors generally require low temperatures of 23 K to 77 K, which can be achieved using cryogenic system employing liquid Hydrogen and liquid Nitrogen respectively, but are still much lower than the room temperature. Thus, observational Room Temperature Superconductivity is considered as the holy grail of modern science, as it can help us in increasing the working temperature range of superconductors and reducing the involved costs and weight of cryogenics. Recent developments in experimental physics do show promise in finding Room Temperature Superconductors. A group of scientists from USA and China have lately discovered that some carbonaceous sulfur hydrides show Room Temperature Superconductivity at very high pressures (around 155 to 400 gigapascals), with the transition temperature of around 200 K [42, 43]. It is suggested that with some chemical tuning of the system, the superconductor's room temperature properties can be retained at lower pressures as well, which will be a major breakthrough in modern science and technology.

2.1.3 Flux vortices and flux pinning

Type II superconductors exist in a ‘mixed’ state between H_{c1} and H_{c2} , where the Meissner effect falls apart and there is some influx of magnetic field in the material. This magnetic flux enters the superconductor through small vortices (Figure 2.4), where the core inside the vortices is not superconducting. Then, the material now only has to expel a fraction of external field since most of the magnetic field passes through the vortex, thus keeping the superconducting state for much higher applied fields than Type I superconductors.

According to Alexei Abrikosov, who proposed this theory in 1957, the flux enters the superconductor in form of quantum ϕ_0 , which is known as Abrikosov vortex or fluxon. It was just a theoretical prediction, but since then scientists have proven the existence of flux vortices and flux lattice. For example, Essmann, Trauble, Harada, and Tonomura observed the flux lines using an electron microscope [44–47]. Other studies were done using Neutron diffraction, Hall Probe microscopes, and video holograms, where flux line single crystals and flux lines were observed [48–51]. The fluxon is in normal phase, with superconducting phase outside, and has supercurrents circulating around the normal region. The normal core is the size of ξ , the Ginzburg-Landau parameter for superconducting coherence length, and the decay of supercurrents is at a distance of λ (London’s penetration depth) from the core. The value of a single fluxon is $\phi_0 = h/2e$, where h is Planck’s constant, and e is the charge of an electron, which is equal to $2.07 \times 10^{-15} \text{ Tm}^2$. The magnetic flux density of a fluxon for the distance, $r \leq \xi$, is given by

$$B(0) \approx \frac{\phi_0}{2\pi\lambda^2} \ln \kappa. \quad (2.3)$$

Here, κ is the Ginzburg-Landau parameter, and type II superconductors can be differentiated for $\kappa > 1/\sqrt{2}$. The value of ϕ_0 is also an indirect experimental proof of Cooper pairs. These vortices can also be measured and verified by some techniques in lab like Bitter Decoration [52], Scanning Tunneling Spectroscopy (STM) [53] [54], and muon-Spin Rotation (μ SR) [55] [56] methods. The high anisotropy of High Temperature Superconductors changes the structure of flux vortices, where the vortex formation depends on the layered arrangement of these materials. The currents can flow in the superconducting parts as long as they avoid the vortex cores. This current causes vortex movement resulting in a macroscopic resistance, and, thus, power loss, as explained below.

When a transport current \mathbf{J} is applied, the fluxon faces a Driving force per unit length $\mathbf{f}_D = \mathbf{J} \times \phi_0$. The Driving force density over a number of vortices, thus, will be

Figure 2.4: Pinning force, F_p , versus the Driving force, F_D , under the influence of applied field, B .

$$\mathbf{F}_D = \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}. \quad (2.4)$$

If \mathbf{v} is the velocity of moving flux line, then the value of electric field induced by the Driving force, in perpendicular direction to the motion and the direction of the field can be given as [57]

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{v}. \quad (2.5)$$

Also, no material is perfect, and comes with defects and impurities. It has been seen that the fluxons (or vortices) are attracted to defects, where the material becomes normal or with reduced superconductivity (could be nanoparticles of some other material, line defects, grain boundaries, vacancies, or defects made by fast neutron radiation), being called pinning centres. These pinning centres avoid the vortex motion due to the influence of driving force. Due to this effect, material scientists place impurities or defects intentionally in the material in order to pin the fluxon at one point to avoid the appearance of electric fields and, consequently, energy loss. The maximum theoretical Pinning force exerted by the impurity to hold a fluxon at its position is approximately [29] [58]

$$F_p = \frac{\phi_0}{16\pi\lambda^2\xi}. \quad (2.6)$$

In Figure 2.4, for pinning to exist, the maximum Pinning force, F_p , should be greater than the Driving Force, F_D . Furthermore, there is a finite critical current density, J_c above which the vortices depin and move. If the Driving force of the superconductor is stronger than the Pinning force, the vortices start moving, but if the Driving force is later switched off, the vortices again rearrange themselves in a stable state where they are pinned again. Pinning varies in a great amount for different type II superconductors. For example,

the critical current value in bulks made of BSCCO (Bismuth Strontium Calcium Coper Oxide) and REBCO is lower than in tapes made of same material, due to the lower texture in bulks. Indeed, in REBCO thin films, the J_c value can be as high as 10^{11} Am^{-2} by achieving a high texture and incorporating a high number of defects, the size of which roughly corresponds to the coherence lengths.

2.2 Critical State Model

A hysteresis effect is observed in superconductors with high pinning (or hard superconductors) under the influence of external applied field, and there is an inherent irreversible magnetization. This process has been explained effectively for macroscopic features by C.P. Bean in his Critical State Model (CSM). The magnetic field enters type II superconductors in form of current vortices, with non-uniform vortex distribution over the superconductor volume being the reason for its magnetization.

The Bean model [59] [60] assumes that the current density never crosses the threshold critical current density, J_c , of the material related to the Pinning force's density [61]. The Critical State Model has been very important, and has been used to find formulas for the magnetization and field distribution of several shapes, where J_c has been considered to be constant [62].

The Critical State Model postulates that a current with critical current density, J_c , is induced by any electromotive force in a superconductor. This can be written mathematically as [63] [64]

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mathbf{J} \leq J_c, \text{ and} \\ \text{any,} & \text{if } \mathbf{J} = J_c. \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

For infinitely long geometries in transverse applied magnetic field or cylinders of finite or infinite thickness, $|J|$ can only be 0 or J_c , but that is not the case for general thin films or 3D shapes [65].

The Maxwell equations that are related with this model are the Biot Savart Law

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J}, \quad (2.8)$$

and Faraday's Law

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}. \quad (2.9)$$

2.2. CRITICAL STATE MODEL

Figure 2.5: Field and current density profiles of field and current density inside a superconducting slab, while (a, b, c) increasing, and (d, e, f) decreasing the amplitude of external field, B_a .

The Critical State Model can explain the magnetization of a superconducting slab in detail, which can be seen in Figures 2.5 (a)-(f). Consider a slab of width $2a$ in the x axis, infinite dimensions in y and z axes, and the applied field, B_a , parallel to the y axis. Here, in the thesis, we use the terms ‘magnetic flux density’ and ‘magnetic field’ interchangeably, as we do not take magnetic materials into account, and, hence, it is assumed that the magnetic field generated by the superconductors is only due to the macroscopic superconducting currents, following $\mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{H}$.

On increasing the external field B_a , screening currents, with $|\mathbf{J}| = J_c$, are induced at the edges of the slab, according to Lenz’s law, which are in the x direction as there is only one component of the field, being in the y direction.

Thus, the profile of magnetic field penetration is simply a straight line (Figure 2.5)(a), with critical current density, J_c , as its slope, which can be explained by the Ampere's law

$$\frac{-\partial B_y}{\partial x} = J_z, \quad (2.10)$$

or, to state the only possibilities for a slab:

$$\frac{\partial B_y}{\partial x} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{or} \\ \pm \mu_0 J_c. \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

The penetration of the current density in the slab sample is with positive J_c from the left and negative J_c from the right, which is due to the fact that the applied field is shielded from the screening currents following the 'right hand rule', and opposing the applied field. These screening currents from the edges also totally shield the center region with no current density from the applied field.

With the increase in field, the field keeps penetrating, and the profile of field and current density changes. The value of the applied field at which the the field penetrates to the center of the slab is known as the penetration field of superconductor, as can be seen in Figure 2.5(b). The current density at this stage penetrates fully till the center of the slab. The value of this parallel penetration field B_p , for a slab is

$$B_p = \mu_0 J_c a, \quad (2.12)$$

where, $2a$ is the thickness of the sample.

After the field intensity is increased above the value of penetration field, the screening currents will not further shield the increase in the field inside, as the current density cannot exceed J_c under the Critical State Model, and, thus, the field profile simply moves upward, as can be seen in Figure 2.5(c).

On decreasing the field strength, the screening currents again start opposing this change from the edges, and the current density switches its sign (Figure 2.5 (d)), thus making the magnetic field profile oppositely linear at the edges. Later, as the field strength is decreased more, the screening currents, with opposite sign, become more prominent. The field inside the superconductor is also penetrated fully till center, and (Figure 2.5 (e)). Here, if the external field is switched off, some field is retained by the superconductor, and is known as the trapped field of the superconductor. On further decreasing the field strength, this profile stays constant, and simply moves further down in magnitude (Figure 2.5(f)).

The behavior of current density penetration for thin films can also be obtained from the Critical State Model. Here, since the film is very thin, a penetration of screening current density magnitude below J_c occurs to the center of the sample in the initial magnetization stage. The magnetic field is zero or ‘frozen’ in this zone ($|J| < J_c$), which is called as sub-critical zone. The magnetic field changes in the zone where $|J| = J_c$. With increase in the applied field, the current density penetrates further into the center, and it takes infinite applied field to completely saturate the thin film with $|\mathbf{J}| = J_c$ [66–68].

It has been experimentally found that the critical current density is a function of the magnetic field, but the original Bean model considers that J_c is independent of the magnetic field B . This assumption can always be taken when the sample is submitted to a uniform applied magnetic field with a bias contribution, \mathbf{B}_b , whose magnitude is much larger than both the superconductor self-field and the variation of the applied magnetic field during the hysteresis cycle.

2.3 E-J Power Law and flux creep

The drawback of the Bean’s model is that it assumes zero resistivity at $|J| < J_c$, and infinite differential resistivity at the critical current $|J| = J_c$. It cannot be applied in its totality to type II superconductors as the actual $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J})$ relation is smooth, and finite flux-creep resistance can be seen near the critical current density, J_c [69] [58]. Then, Bean’s model does not explain the relaxation of the vortex density over time. Thus, for practical applications of superconductors, E-J Power Law is used widely in scientific community for numerical formulations based on Maxwell equations.

The Power Law explains the phenomenon of flux creep for $|\mathbf{J}|$ close to J_c where the superconductor loses its magnetization gradually over time in a logarithmic way, leading to stable fields and currents. Kim, Hempstead, and Strnad [70] observed this decay of currents in hollow cylinders, and described the transition at critical transport currents for hard superconductors. This flux creep can be visible by either trapped flux changes and/or small resistive voltages. Anderson [65] proposed a theory stating that the thermally activated flux creep may constitute a number of flux lines jumping over the pinning sites/barriers in form of bundles together, and the jump rate of them can be given by

$$v = v_0 e^{\frac{-E_{eff}}{kT}}, \quad (2.13)$$

where, v_0 is the characteristic frequency, and E_{eff} is the energy barrier from

the pinning mechanism being affected by the driving force, also known as Effective Activation Energy. The generalized $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J})$ relationship is given as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J}) = E_c \cdot e^{\frac{-u(|\mathbf{J}|)}{kT}} \frac{\mathbf{J}}{|\mathbf{J}|}, \quad (2.14)$$

and

$$u(\mathbf{J}) = u_0 \left[\left(\frac{J_c}{|\mathbf{J}|} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}, \quad (2.15)$$

where, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, u is the activation energy, and u_0 and α are constants. This model is simple, and it matches excellently with the experimental data too. For many experimental situations, usually at $|\mathbf{J}|$ close to J_c , it is observed that $\alpha \ll 1$ [71]. Then, the electric field and $u(\mathbf{J})$ in the superconductor is related to the critical current density as

$$u(\mathbf{J}) = u_0 \ln \left(\frac{J_c}{|\mathbf{J}|} \right), \quad (2.16)$$

and

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J}) = E_c \left(\frac{|\mathbf{J}|}{J_c} \right)^n \frac{\mathbf{J}}{|\mathbf{J}|}, \quad (2.17)$$

where, E_c is the voltage criterion or critical electric field, usually equal to 10^{-4} V/m, J_c is the critical current density, and n determines the slope of the curve in log-log scale. The n value decrease with the temperature and the magnetic field. At $n = 1$, we get linear resistivity for normal conductors, for example, copper. At $n \rightarrow \infty$, the Critical State Model is reproduced, as can be seen in Figure 2.6. Higher n makes more stable magnets at constant B , but they are less reliable for over-currents [32]. Therefore, the E-J characteristic is considered to be an important design input for superconducting applications. A high quality material sample usually has high n value. For typical persistent magnets, this value should ideally be between 50-100, although, HTS magnets can present n values below 30 [72]. For REBCO tapes at 77 K in self field, the n value is around 30 to 40 and could be above for certain materials, such as 100 for NbTi at 4 K and low B .

On application of external field to a slab, the currents penetrate from the edges. On doing so, the screening currents also shield the center region of the sample from external field. The current density is zero in the center till the

Figure 2.6: E-J Power Law for different n values, as compared with the Critical State Model (equation (2.7)). We use power law with exponent 30 in this thesis.

sample becomes saturated on the application of field of higher strength, where the current density occupies the whole area of the sample. An example of this smoothing of the current front can be seen in Figure 2.7 [73–75]. It can also be seen here that E-J Power Law allows for current density higher than J_c in the sample, which makes this relation more realistic than the Critical State Model.

Additionally, the resistivity of the superconductor can be analyzed from the relation

$$\mathbf{E} = \rho \mathbf{J}. \quad (2.18)$$

Thus, substituting the Power Law in 2.18, gives

$$\rho(\mathbf{J}) = \frac{E_c}{J_c} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{J}|}{J_c} \right)^{n-1}. \quad (2.19)$$

Figure 2.7: Current density profile for an infinitely long square bar under applied magnetic field in the y direction assuming E-J Power Law. The screening current penetrates from the edges and shields the center region on application of external field.

2.4 Superconducting motors

Electric motors were first invented in 1890s, and after some early development, the basic underlying technology has not changed significantly for the last 50 years. The reason behind them not being perfectly efficient is the power loss due to mechanical friction, resistance in the windings of metal wires, and induction loss at the ferromagnetic parts.

Fully superconducting motors are those where the normal magnets or electromagnets in the rotor and/or stator are replaced by superconducting magnets, as can be seen in Figure 2.8. Superconducting AC synchronous motors are different than normal motors, as they use superconducting wires in their coil windings instead of conventional copper coils [76]. These superconducting windings can carry much larger currents than copper windings and, thus, are capable of generating very high magnetic fields with less volume and weight. Superconducting stacks of tapes or bulks can also be used in the rotor of the motor as permanent magnets or to build a coil (Figure 2.8), instead of copper wires or permanent ferromagnets, having several advantages, which are discussed in next section.

The major advantage of using a superconducting motor is the compact size,

Figure 2.8: A fully superconducting motor sketch by Oswald Elektromotoren GmbH for ASuMED project [14]. HTS stacks and bulks can be used in the rotors of the motor.

due to its higher power density, with the size reduction of almost 70 percent as compared to the conventional motors [77]. This also helps in reducing the weight of the system, and, thus, reducing the developmental and operational costs of such machines, along with faster delivery and installation times. For applications in aviation and other mobile industries, where weight reduction is a major factor, superconducting motors can be of great use. Energy saving is another major benefit of using large HTS motors due to its increased efficiency. For example, for a 5 MW conventional motor, a 1 percent efficiency increase by using HTS material can save up to 430 MWh of electricity every year. Also, the HTS motors have much lighter weight, and present significant noise and vibration reduction. Furthermore, during transients, the HTS motors are more electrically stable as compared to normal motors, due to their operation at smaller load angles at 15 degrees as compared to 70 degrees of conventional motors, and higher peak torque capabilities of up to 300 percent, and, thus, can face large oscillatory torques without any loss of synchronous speeds [77].

Electric motors currently hold 1.2 billion dollar of annual share globally, predicted to be quadrupled over next decade. Due to their lower acquisition and operating costs, superconducting motors are particularly attractive for applications where size and weight are important factors, and, thus, the major market for these motors are public sectors (like marine and aircraft propulsion) with minimum requirement of atleast 750 kW power. There has been a lot of research and development in this field already. For example, a 70 MW-class superconducting generator (LTS) by the Japanese Super-GM program, an 1800 rpm synchronous condenser by American Superconductors, 300kW motor and 3600 rpm generator by Siemens, 30 kW motor for electric cars by

Sumitomo Electric, a 3.6 MW ship propulsion motor by TECO-Westinghouse, and a 1.7 MW hydroelectric power generator by Converteam were developed recently in last decade [78] [13]. Currently, a 1 MW fully superconducting motor demonstrator for hybrid electric aircraft is in development phase under ASuMED project [14], and American Superconductors now produces HTS motors for ship propulsion. U.S. Navy is currently considering an all-electric ship systems, including propulsion, and the requirement, that they had in the year 2001 for 5 MW power, has increased to up to 36.5 MW by 2008 [79] [80]. In addition to that, electrifying civil sea transport has potential to reduce emissions by high amounts, especially in ferries and cruisers. GE also built a 1 MW, 10 krpm motor for aerospace application, and in general a 2.6 MW motor is projected to have 90 percent electric drive system efficiency and 12 percent fuel reduction for 3500 nautical miles [13].

2.5 Cross-field demagnetization

High Temperature Superconductors are able to contain or ‘trap’ large amounts of magnetic fields, staying magnetized for long periods of times, and, thus, they can be used for major engineering applications such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), MRI machines, high power density motors, and magnetic bearings. In superconducting motors, generators, and bearings, the conventional permanent magnets in the rotors can be replaced by superconducting stacks of tapes (Figure 2.8). The world record of trapped magnetic field in stacks of REBCO superconducting layers is 17.7 T [81], which slightly outperform bulk superconductors. A field of up to 17.6 T magnetic field at 26K in a stack of two silver-doped GdBCO SC-bulks has also been trapped [82]. These are much higher trapped fields than those for conventional permanent magnets, being up to 3 T only.

Superconductors can, though, feel adverse effects under ripple or alternating in crossed magnetic fields, which can reduce the amount of trapped field and magnetization stored in the stacks or bulks of the material. Demagnetization can be caused by either alternating or rotating fields applied in a tranverse direction to the original magnetization (Figure 2.9) [83], with rotating field being more severe in causing demagnetization [15]. The most adverse effect of demagnetization is observed, in rotating field, when the ripple field is applied orthogonally to the magnetizing current direction and, in most cases, it can largely reduce the magnetization. We call this field as ripple field or cross field interchangeably in this thesis, B_r . Although demagnetization can be used for our benefit as an effect to reduce shielding currents in superconducting magnets [84], it can be a very negative feature for other major applications like motors and generators, and, hence, a solution is required to

Figure 2.9: Demagnetization of a superconducting stack can be caused by application of magnetic field in transverse direction.

be found to consider their continuous application. Although some studies have already been done on cross-field demagnetization, it has not been possible to model superconducting layers thinner than $10 \mu\text{m}$ and stacks of more than 10 tapes, being realistic stacks consisting of around $2 \mu\text{m}$ thin superconductors, and between 50-100 tapes [16–23]. Thus, this is a very important research area where further detailed modeling and experimental studies are required to be made.

Next, we outline the magnetization and demagnetization configuration that we consider in this thesis. The general process is to first magnetize the stack of tapes using Field Cool process, where a magnetic field greater than H_{c1} is applied to the stack. When it is in the normal state ($T > T_c$) (Figure 2.10 (a)), and later the superconductor is cooled below T_c (2.10 (b)). Next, the applied field is reduced to zero (2.10 (c)), and finally the sample is left to relax for some minutes. By doing so, the superconducting stack is able to trap some amount of magnetic field (Figure 2.10 (c)). The sample saturates when the initial applied field, B_i , is the penetration field for applied fields perpendicular to the wide face of the tape, which we call ‘perpendicular applied field’.

Later, a transverse or crossed field is applied to the stack of tapes which reduces the amount of trapped field in the sample [85], as seen in Figure 2.10

Figure 2.10: Qualitative sketch of the demagnetization process of stack of tapes during (a) normal state, (b) magnetization through Field-Cool process, (c) trapped magnetic field on top of the stack, and (d) cross field demagnetization through application of ripple field.

(d). Demagnetization of irreversible type-II superconductors in crossed fields can be explained by numerical modeling including assumptions from the material properties, like E-J Power Law and Critical State Theory Model. Since the E-J Power Law Model is easily comparable to Critical State results, the Critical State Model is maybe the simplest model to understand the magnetization behavior of superconductors.

An increased amount of magnetization can be obtained by using a ferromagnetic layer interscalated between the superconductor, as opposed to just simple superconducting stacks, since in some cases it can raise the trapped flux by up to 50 percent [15] and lower the rate of demagnetization. However, the ferromagnetic substrate is only effective if it is below saturation, specially for the demagnetization. It has also been proven experimentally [16] that, for large ripple fields, the stacks of tapes face less amount of demagnetization as compared to superconducting bulks, which can lose up to 50 percent of magnetization by just the application of 1 cycle of ripple field.

The demagnetization decay depends on various factors. It gets faster when the thickness of a tape (for the same sheet critical current density) or frequency of the applied rotating field is increased. Demagnetization is larger for rotating fields than that for crossed field configurations [15], though the frequency of crossed ripple field has very low impact on the demagnetizing effect of per cycle, being lower for higher frequency [16] [86]. The demagnetization rate factor is also ripple field dependent, which increases when the amplitude of applied ripple field is increased. The direction of the applied crossed field also plays a crucial role in demagnetization. It has been proven numerically that, for a thin strip, the decay rate or relaxation for longitudinal shaking is slower and qualitatively different than transverse shaking [87].

As explained in Section 3.2.1, after a certain transient, the trapped field decays exponentially for large enough fields, and this trapped field can be estimated analytically under the Critical State Model assumptions, as done for a single tape in [88]. For thin samples like tapes, this decay requires many cycles [19].

When a ripple field is applied in transverse direction, the newly induced current density changes the original current profile in the sample [16]. An example of a fast change in current profile due to cross field application of high ripple field can be seen in Figure (2.11), obtained during this PhD [89]. Figure (2.11) (b) shows the typical S current profile for demagnetization.

Similarly, the increase of transverse field will decrease the demagnetization time [86]. The decay constant also depends on the number of tapes in the stack, which increases proportionally with increase in the number of tapes, leading to the slow demagnetization of the stack [19, 83] [86]. The demagneti-

Figure 2.11: Current density distribution (a) after Field-Cool magnetization (applied field parallel to x- axis), and (b) after 30 cycles of cross magnetic field (ripple field parallel to y- axis), calculated by our numerical method for 1 tape of $2 \mu\text{m}$ thickness with power law exponent as 30 (Section 3.1.1).

zation rate of superconducting stacks can also be lowered by shielding it with layers on the sides, having a positive effect [16] [18]. The rate of change of magnetization is analyzed in detail in Section 4.

2.5.1 Dynamic Magneto-Resistance

The question arises that what is the reason behind cross field demagnetization. This behavior is caused because of an intrinsic property of superconductors, or a dissipative effect, called Dynamic Magneto-Resistance (DMR) [19,88,90–92].

In superconducting motors and generators, the background ripple fields (mostly generated by stator) cause transverse AC fields, that superconductors face constantly. A DC voltage rises when a transverse AC magnetic field, above a certain threshold, is applied to a superconducting tape. This voltage opposes the already present DC transport current in the superconductor, and, thus, gives rise to a dynamic magneto-resistance or "effective resistance" (Figure 2.12). This dynamic resistance causes the decay of the static magnetizing currents, which can be regarded as DC currents in sections of the tape. Consequently, this causes dropping of trapped fields, and, hence, the demagnetization of superconductors. This resistance also causes an additional power loss, and is required to be considered when calculating the total loss in superconductor, which also involves magnetization loss [91] [93]. The transverse applied ripple magnetizing field (or "ripple field") causes DC electric field generated inside the superconductor that is directly proportional to the transverse field amplitude and inversely proportional to the critical current density. As stated by Brandt and Mikitik [94], their theory explains that this DC electric field increases with the amplitude of transverse magnetic field, causing an increase of the decay rate of magnetization.

This relaxation of magnetization in a thin tape can be understood by the 'walking-motion' of vortices [88,94]. Being said that, the Critical State Model can also explain the dynamic magneto-resistance, and, thus, the presence of superconducting vortices is not strictly required [92] [95]. Using the Critical State Model, the dynamic resistance in AC parallel applied field, B_r , for a slab with a given transport current I is equal to

$$R(I) = \frac{2fdl}{I_c} [B_{ra} - B_{th}(I)], \quad (2.20)$$

where, B_{th} , B_{ra} , f , d , l , and I_c are the threshold field, ripple field amplitude, ripple field frequency, tape thickness, tape length, and critical current, respectively.

Figure 2.12: Dynamic magneto-resistance is caused when an AC cross field gives rise to a DC voltage, which opposes the present DC transport current in superconductor.

For a slab facing parallel AC field under Critical State Model, the threshold field is equal to [88]

$$B_{\text{th}}(I) = \frac{\mu_0 J_c d}{2} \left(1 - \frac{|I|}{I_c}\right), \quad (2.21)$$

where, the critical current $I_c = wdJ_c$, with w and J_c being the width and critical current density, respectively.

Below this threshold field, there is a shielded region of ‘frozen flux’ within the center of superconductor, which does not allow any change in field to be experienced by the DC transport current flowing in this shielded region. Thus, the dynamic magneto-resistance is zero below threshold field since no flux crosses the superconductor [92]. This thesis uses the dynamic magneto-resistance property of superconductors to build an effective E-J relation (Section 4.2.1), which allows us to calculate demagnetization of superconducting stacks for millions of cycles of applied transverse field in a relatively very short time.

2.6 Thermal quench

A quench is the premature stoppage of the operation of a superconducting magnet when a section of the magnet enters resistive state. This can occur when the net current of a part exceeds the critical current (I_c) by a considerable amount. This results in raising the temperature of that section or spot above critical temperature (T_c), generally known as a ‘hotspot’, being subjected to the joule heating (ρJ^2) by the high amount of current. It can lead to the increase of temperature in the surrounding regions as well, thus pushing them into the normal or resistive state. Consequently, the whole magnet can become normal in a matter of milliseconds [24, 25, 96]. This can have disastrous effects on a HTS magnet or coil, with an ability to destroy the magnet. For example, this happened recently in 2008 when a major section of superconducting magnets at the Large Hadron Collider (CERN) unanticipatedly quenched, and had to be replaced at once, costing millions of euros to the agency [97].

Understanding the mechanics of thermal quench is of utmost importance for safe operation of a superconducting magnet. There has been a lot of research on the quench behavior of LTS magnets, but the quench propagation of HTS based magnets is yet to be fully understood, as they show very different quantitative behaviors [24]. Normal Zone Propagation Velocity (or NZPV) and Minimum Quench Energy (MQE) are the properties of a superconductor used to define the ability of a superconducting magnet to quench rapidly. It is seen that the NZPV is orders of magnitude slower in HTS magnets as compared to LTS magnets, whereas the corresponding MQE is much higher in HTS magnets than LTS magnets [98–101]. For coated conductors, the NZPV is expected to be very small [102–104].

The quench, though unexpected, is part of a superconducting magnet’s normal operation, and, thus, there should be a mandatory quench protection system installed, as to prevent any kind of damage to the magnet. One way to protect superconducting magnets from quench is to force the remaining current in the magnet to flow across a shunt resistance in parallel, which dissipates the energy in the magnet. Some high field magnets, like the 32 T magnet in MagLab, contain a heater on each HTS pancake coil that rapidly transit the whole magnet to normal state, once quench is detected at any point, rapidly decreasing the current in the magnet.

Characteristic temperatures of coolants		
Cryogen	Boiling Point [K]	Critical Point [K]
Helium	4.2	5.2
Hydrogen	20.4	33.2
Nitrogen	77.3	126.2
Oxygen	90.2	154.6
Methane	111.6	190.5

Table 2.2: Different thermodynamic characteristics of cryogenes used as coolants for superconductors.

2.6.1 Non-linear heat exchange of superconductor with liquid Nitrogen

Generally, liquid Nitrogen and/or liquid Helium is used to cool superconductors below the required critical temperature. There are various other options as well for low temperature cryogenes (Table 2.2), but given the ease of procurement, lesser risk of occupational hazards, and other thermodynamic benefits, Helium and Nitrogen are used in majority. Out of Nitrogen and Helium, Nitrogen's latent heat of evaporation (199 kJ/kg) is an order of magnitude larger than that of Helium (21 kJ/kg), which translates to ten times lower boil-off mass flow for Nitrogen for a given heat load [105]. This makes Nitrogen a more effective cryogen than Helium to extract large enthalpies. Contrastingly, Helium vapours have a larger cooling capacity than that of Nitrogen, which can also be used to cool down components in high-field magnets. Also, the triple point of Helium is virtually non-existent, so that it can solidify only over pressures of 2.5 MPa [106], which makes it the most used coolant in the current and historical superconducting applications. Interestingly, extracting heat at lower temperatures of Helium increases the cost factor by more than 50 in high-field magnets, for instance the ones in Large Hadron Collider (LHC), which is one of the major benefits of using liquid Nitrogen as a coolant over liquid Helium [105].

For superconductors in contact with liquid Nitrogen, a strongly non-linear convection at the boundary exists (as we consider in this thesis- Figure 3.3), which leads to a boiling heat transfer. This non-linearity, in the heat flux versus temperature difference, is because of the higher temperature of the 'solid' superconductor surface than the saturation temperature of the liquid Nitrogen [106], and can be seen in Figure 3.5. At low temperature difference between the superconductor and the Nitrogen bath in this figure, there is natural convection between the superconductor and liquid Nitrogen (a), but as the temperature difference increases, nucleate boiling occurs (b), in which the vapor bubbles are generated locally on the superconductor surface. At

the maximum heat transfer coefficient, called as peak-nucleate boiling flux, the bubbles combine into a sustained film on the superconductor surface, which greatly limits the heat transfer (d). Here, a ‘local’ hysteresis loop can be formed when the temperature difference is afterwards reduced below the aforementioned film-boiling state. However, the initial point of the hysteresis curve may not be the same as the previous one in the nucleate-boiling section (known as transition boiling- (c) in Figure 3.5). The Peak Nucleate Boiling flux, or PNBF, for Nitrogen ($100,000 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$) is much higher than that of Helium ($10,000 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$), which makes liquid Nitrogen a much better candidate in pool boiling of a superconductor, as it increases the maximum heat flux limit that can be released from a hot object like a quenching magnet [106–108]. Naturally, the higher boiling temperature of Nitrogen compared to Helium needs to be compatible with the operation temperature of the superconducting material in the particular application.

2.7 General modeling methods

The field of numerical modeling of materials has been on boom in current times, since the inception of high speed and powerful computing systems at every engineer’s desks. The benefit of fast results, flexibility of choosing and altering parameters, non-intrusive analysis of materials, riddance from expensive experimental setups, faster comparisons, and re-evaluation and easily shareable result data are some of the motivating factors behind this trend.

Analytical solutions can be found for superconductors, but they are limited to simple geometries and uniform external magnetic fields, due to their non-linear behavior. This non-linearity can be taken into account by numerical methods, which are a bit complex but effective in nature, with the major drawbacks being computationally expensive and, in some cases, having stability issues [109] [110]. For high temperature superconductors, various Finite Element Methods (FEM), and Variational principle methods can be used for modeling and analysis, some of which are stated below.

2.7.1 Electro-Magnetic models

FEM in H formulation

One of the most famous and widely used Finite Element Method for superconductors is H - formulation, which solves for the magnetic field. As the partial differential equations for this system can be easily substituted in commercial

software like COMSOL, ANSYS, or FreeFEM++ PDE solver modules, this model has gained a lot of popularity.

If we neglect the displacement current term, the Maxwell equations for the Faraday and Biot Savart Law can be stated as

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \quad (2.22)$$

and

$$\mathbf{J} = \nabla \times \mathbf{H}, \quad (2.23)$$

with constitutive relations

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu(\mathbf{H})\mathbf{H}, \quad (2.24)$$

and

$$\mathbf{E} = \rho(\mathbf{J})\mathbf{J}. \quad (2.25)$$

The main equation to be solved in H -formulation comes from combining the above equations, which are given as

$$\nabla \times (\rho(\nabla \times \mathbf{H})\nabla \times \mathbf{H}) = -\frac{\partial(\mu\mathbf{H})}{\partial t}, \quad (2.26)$$

where, $\rho(\mathbf{J})$ for this model can be calculated by Power Law for superconductors [111], being

$$\rho(\mathbf{J}) = \frac{E_c}{J_c} \left| \frac{\mathbf{J}}{J_c} \right|^{n-1}, \quad (2.27)$$

which is valid for both 2D (infinitely long geometries in transverse applied field) and 3D modeling.

For infinitely long geometries, the induced net current (I_{total}) for the whole domain can be used in the model using the equation

$$I_{total} = \int_S J_z dS = \oint_{\partial S} d\mathbf{l} \cdot \mathbf{H}, \quad (2.28)$$

which, for each conductor, is

$$I_i = \int_{S_i} J_z dS = \oint_{\partial S_i} d\mathbf{l} \cdot \mathbf{H}, \quad (2.29)$$

with S_i being the cross section of each superconductor region. For magnetization problems, $I_{total} = 0$.

Also, \mathbf{H} at the external boundary of the modeling domain is,

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} I_{total} \frac{\mathbf{e}_\phi}{|\mathbf{r}|} + \mathbf{H}_a, \quad (2.30)$$

where, H_a is the applied magnetic field, and \mathbf{e} is the unit vector in the angular direction.

FEM in \mathbf{A} formulation

Another efficient modeling method is the A formulation, in which the partial differential equations are solved for the magnetic vector potential \mathbf{A} . From Maxwell equations, the basic equations for this model look like

$$\mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} - \nabla \phi, \quad (2.31)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}, \quad (2.32)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}, \quad (2.33)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu(\mathbf{H})\mathbf{H}, \quad (2.34)$$

and

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma(\mathbf{E})\mathbf{E}, \quad (2.35)$$

where, $\nabla \phi$ is scalar voltage gradient. To be noted, this formulation is valid for any gauge. Thus, the main equations to be solved, found by combining these equations, are given by [109]

$$\nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} \mathbf{B} = \sigma(\mathbf{E})\mathbf{E}, \quad (2.36)$$

and

$$\nabla \times \left(\frac{1}{\mu} \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \right) = \sigma \left(-\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} - \nabla \phi \right) \left(-\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} - \nabla \phi \right), \quad (2.37)$$

where $\nabla \phi$ is determined from the constraints as follows. In infinitely long problems, $\mathbf{A} = A \mathbf{e}_z$ and $\mathbf{J} = J \mathbf{e}_z$, so that $\nabla \phi = \partial_z \phi \mathbf{e}_z$, and $\partial_z \phi$ is uniform at each conductor cross section. Then, the current constraints follow

$$I_i = \int_{S_i} dS J = \int_{S_i} dS \sigma (-\partial_t A - (\partial_z \phi)_i) \quad (2.38)$$

for each conductor, and

$$I_{total} = \int_S dS J \quad (2.39)$$

for the whole modeling domain.

Additionally, infinitely long problems require proper boundary conditions far away from the sample. By imposing the boundary condition, we impose the gauge. In Coulomb's gauge, the external boundary condition is

$$A = -\frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} I_{total} \ln |\mathbf{r}| + A_a(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2.40)$$

where, A_a is the vector potential caused by an external applied magnetic field.

FEM in \mathbf{T} - Ω formulation

This formulation uses the current vector potential \mathbf{T} and magnetic scalar potential Ω for modeling the superconductor interaction with magnetic materials. Since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0$, we can define \mathbf{T} as

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{J}. \quad (2.41)$$

From,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}, \quad (2.42)$$

we obtain that $\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \nabla \times \mathbf{T}$, and, hence,

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{T} - \nabla \Omega, \quad (2.43)$$

for any Ω , since $\nabla \times \nabla\Omega = 0$. Using the constitutive relations, where μ and ρ are generally non-linear,

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu\mathbf{H}, \quad (2.44)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \rho\mathbf{J}, \quad (2.45)$$

and the other equations above, Faraday's law, $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\partial_t\mathbf{B}$, becomes [112]

$$\nabla \times (\rho\nabla \times \mathbf{T}) = -\frac{\partial\mu(\mathbf{T} - \nabla\Omega)}{\partial t}. \quad (2.46)$$

Additionally, $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ becomes

$$\nabla \cdot (\mu(\mathbf{T} - \nabla\Omega)) = 0, \quad (2.47)$$

where, equations (2.46) and (2.47) constitutes the T- Ω formulation.

In infinitely long geometries, the current constraints are

$$I_i = \int_{S_i} dS J_z = \oint_{\partial S_i} d\mathbf{l} \times \mathbf{T}, \quad (2.48)$$

on each conductor and

$$I_{total} = \oint_{\partial S} d\mathbf{l} \times \mathbf{T}, \quad (2.49)$$

on the whole modeling section.

2.7.2 Electro-Thermal models

Generally, in most problems, the following heat diffusion equation is solved

$$\rho_m C_p(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(k(T)\nabla T) + Q(T), \quad (2.50)$$

where, ρ_m is the mass density, $C_p(T)$ is the specific heat capacity, $k(T)$ is the thermal conductivity, T is the temperature, ∂t is the small change in time, and $Q(T)$ is the heat generated in the superconductor. If no heat is generated, and k is constant, the equation (2.50) can be re-written in 2D space $r = (x, y)$, with temperature $T(x, y, t)$, as

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right), \quad (2.51)$$

where, α is known as the thermal diffusivity, and is given as

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{\rho_m C_p}. \quad (2.52)$$

For a REBCO tape, the normal (ρ_N) and superconducting state (ρ_{SC}) resistivities, respectively, are given by [113]

$$\rho_N = \rho_{T_c} + \beta(T - T_c), \quad (2.53)$$

and, for $T < T_c$,

$$\rho_{SC} = \frac{E_c}{J_c(T)} \left[\frac{|\mathbf{J}|}{J_c(T)} \right]^{n-1}, \quad (2.54)$$

which comes from the Power Law, equation (2.17). Here β is the temperature coefficient, and $J_c(T)$ is the critical current density, which is temperature and critical temperature (T_c) dependent, and, for $T < T_c$, can be modeled as

$$J_c(T) = J_c(T_N) \frac{T_c - T}{T_c - T_N}, \quad (2.55)$$

where, $J_c(T_N)$, T_c , and T_N are critical current density at 77 K (temperature of liquid Nitrogen bath) , critical temperature, and temperature of the surrounding coolant (for example liquid Nitrogen, Helium etc), respectively. For liquid Nitrogen, T_N is 77 K.

Thus, the final resistivity of the superconductor, $\rho_F(J, T)$, is given as

$$\rho_F(J, T) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\rho_N \times \rho_{SC}}{\rho_N + \rho_{SC}} \right), & \text{if } T < T_c, \text{ and} \\ \rho_N, & \text{if } T \geq T_c. \end{cases} \quad (2.56)$$

This final resistivity is used in the calculation of the heat loss, Q , in equation (2.50), when any Electro-Thermal model is coupled with any Electro-Magnetic model.

There are many methods that have been used to solve the above heat diffusion to calculate temperature changes in a superconductor. Bonnard et al expresses their thermal model in the form of electrical circuit elements, assuming temperature as voltage, heat flux as current, and heat capacity as capacitance of the circuit for calculating heat transfer and NZPV using a

simple analogical method [113]. Tixador et al uses Finite Element method to solve for coupled electromagnetic and electrothermal problems, where the electromagnetic part is calculated using A-V formulation [114]. Other uncommon methods for calculating temperature change are Finite Difference Methods [115] and Monte-Carlo simulations [116, 117].

Variational methods

The solution for current density, \mathbf{J} , or temperature, T , both in 2D and 3D, can be found by variational principles such as the Minimum Electro Magnetic Entropy Production, or MEMEP [118], and Minimum Electro Thermal Entropy Production, or METEP, respectively. These methods are much faster and, in some cases, less complex than the previous formulations, since it does not require solving for variables in air. The variational principle methods minimize the functional for entropy production, and it is discussed in details in the next chapter.

2.8 Applications of superconductivity

108 years since the discovery of superconductivity, the superconductor industry has just recently picked up pace in terms of practical world applications such as power, medical, energy, applied sciences, transport etc. The relatively recent discovery of High Temperature Superconductors (HTS) played a pivotal part in this progress, which can provide superior performance as compared to the materials in their relative field of usage. Environmental and economical gains are two of the major motivational factors that has pushed for a scientific development in this industry. Superconductor market is predicted to take off at a very high rate after 2020, with USA, Japan, and Europe being considered as the major consumers of this technology [119]. According to recent reports, the global superconductor market can post up to USD 4.37 billion in the period 2019-2023, growing at a CAGR(Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 1 percent [120,121]. The major superconductor market application is in medical equipments, as can be seen in Figure 2.13. The application in transport shows great promise as well, with a CAGR of 3 percent by 2023 [120]. The benefit of using superconducting materials, when compared to standard electromagnets, is that the external current just needs to be applied only once, which forms closed loops, and as long as the material is under the critical conditions, the current can theoretically persist indefinitely.

For power applications, electric motors and generators are one of the potential implementations of High Temperature Superconductors in the industry,

SUPERCONDUCTOR MARKET SHARE

Figure 2.13: Superconductor market share by applications, for 2016, with a predicted CAGR of 1 percent by 2023. Superconducting motors are being used in transportation, as well as in other applications like wind turbines and generators.

due to the improved efficiency of rotors and stators, and reduction in weight and size. Due to the high current density, HTS motors can be as small as 50 percent compared to conventional motors, with efficiency rate of up to 99 percent [17, 111, 122–124]. Superconducting transformers have more benefits over conventional ones in terms of reduction in the losses in windings [125]. Efficient fault current limiters can be made with superconducting material for faster resistive transitions [126–128]. Superconducting cables can be used for underground power transmission in urban areas due to its high current density. Over 100 miles of underground power transmission wires have to be replaced every year in USA, with a market of around 200 million dollars, and superconducting wires can be one of the most economical solution for this issue [129]. Recently, in 2020, a company from Korea has also successfully completed the Shingal project by connecting two radial substations with a 23 kV HTS cable over a 1 km distance [130]. Superconducting generators are also used in wind turbines and generators, with high power density, reduction in noise/pollution, and ease of maintenance as one of the major benefits over their conventional counterparts [77, 131–133].

The major usage of superconductors is in Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI) machines in medical field, being the first large scale application of these materials [134,135]. They are used for scanning brain and body anomalies in a person, by keeping them under a very powerful electromagnet (could be above 9 T [136]). The electric power supply to the magnet can be switched off once there is current in the superconducting coil, in contrast to the normal electromagnets which have high levels of heat dissipation and large power requirements due to resistance [137]. Furthermore, superconducting electromagnets just require the power supply to maintain the cryogenics to control the operation temperature [138,139]. Very sensitive superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) can be used to detect magnetic fields from heart and brain, which are in the range of 10^{-10} to 10^{-13} T, and, thus, SQUIDS are very useful for non-intrusive medical examinations of sensitive human organs, such as the brain [140–142].

Energy applications for superconductors include superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES), flywheels, and nuclear fusion. SMES stores energy in a magnetic field generated by superconducting coils with high loss-less DC current, and can be used as emergency power source [143,144]. Flywheel discs store energy in form of rotational kinetic energy by staying suspended in the air over a superconducting magnet, and, hence, they can be spun indefinitely due to lack of friction [145,146]. High field superconducting electromagnets are used for scientific research purposes that require high values of intensity fields and energy, such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) [147] or particle accelerators [148]. Nuclear fusion requires a large amount of heat, being heated to up to a million degrees, to generate clean nuclear energy from highly ionized gases. These gases are required to be confined, which is only possible by large superconducting magnets. The present International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) uses this technology, and it is supposed to demonstrate nuclear fusion with collaboration of up to 35 nations, which is scheduled to produce the first plasma by 2025 [149,150].

Superconductors are also used for electric mobility and transportation. Ship propulsion is considered of the major usage of HTS motors, as the weight of the system is not of an immediate concern in this application [13,21,79,151,152]. Magnetic Levitation (MagLev) trains in Japan and China use superconducting magnets. These repel or attract normal magnets at the guideways below, to make the train levitate and move forward at high frictionless speeds. Superconductors are used in the linear HTS motors for conventional high speed or MAGLEV trains [153–158]. Hyperloop is also a very recent application of HTS motors, where linear superconducting motors are used [159–161].

Superconducting motors can be used in hybrid electric aircraft for high power density requirements and greener distributed propulsion system. The ASuMED project aims to demonstrate a 1MW superconducting motor, with

superconducting coils and stacks in its stator and rotor, respectively [14, 162]. These kind of superconducting motors enable distributed electric propulsion in aircraft which can reduce CO₂ emissions by 75 percent, NO_x and particulate emissions by 90 percent, and noise by 65 percent, as compared to its contemporaries from 2000 [13, 163, 164]. In space applications, superconducting flywheels and SMES can be used for energy storage [165, 166]. As well, highly efficient gyroscopes can be made of these advanced materials [167, 168]. Other applications of superconductors in space include space telescopes [169, 170], radiation shielding of spacecraft (for example, SR2S project by CERN) [171–173], and electromagnetic spacecraft propulsion [174–176]. Thus, superconductors are well establishing themselves in the aerospace industry as well.

Chapter 3

Modeling method

While Finite Element Methods (FEM) are good for modeling superconductors, they have some drawbacks as well. The state variables in FEM are solved for both the sample volume and the surrounding air, which results in loss of quite a few degrees of freedom, as the boundary conditions needs to be set away from the sample. The surrounding also needs to be meshed appropriately, which makes the computation complicated and slow, specially for moving mesh. The Minimum Electro-Magnetic Entropy Production, or MEMEP, method is a variational principle modeling technique which aims to solve these problems, which is discussed in details in this chapter. MEMEP concentrates on the interaction between the elements of the superconducting sample, and, thus, the surrounding air can be ignored in the computation using more degrees of freedom for the sample volume. This method also uses J as a variable, which in 2D is a scalar, thus greatly reducing the degrees of freedom. This helps in much faster calculations, and more efficient results [118]. Similarly, to solve for temperature in superconductors, an original variational principle method- Minimum Electro-Thermal Entropy Production (METEP) can be used, which is also discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Electro-Magnetic modeling : Numerical method

3.1.1 Variational principle method- MEMEP

The MEMEP method is a type of \mathbf{J} formulation that minimizes the entropy production, which is given in the form of a functional. Minimizing this functional at every time step is the same as solving the equation for the vector potential in Coulomb's gauge [177]. The current density for a given applied

vector potential \mathbf{A}_a and electrostatic potential ϕ is given as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J}) = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}[\mathbf{J}]}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_a}{\partial t} - \nabla \phi, \quad (3.1)$$

where, $\mathbf{A}[\mathbf{J}]$ is the vector potential in Coulomb's gauge generated by \mathbf{J} , which is related to \mathbf{J} as [57]

$$\mathbf{A}[\mathbf{J}](\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}, \quad (3.2)$$

and satisfies

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0. \quad (3.3)$$

Solving equation (3.2) is the same as minimizing the functional F in equation (3.4) for the change in current density between two time steps, $\Delta \mathbf{J}$, and can be verified by solving the Euler Lagrange equations for the functional [178].

$$F(\Delta \mathbf{J}) = \int_V dV \left(\frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{J} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{A}[\Delta \mathbf{J}]}{\Delta t} + \Delta \mathbf{J} \cdot \frac{\Delta \mathbf{A}_a}{\Delta t} + U(\mathbf{J}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{J}) + \nabla \phi(\mathbf{J}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{J}) \right), \quad (3.4)$$

where, V is the sample volume, \mathbf{J}_0 is the current density at the end of the previous time step t_0 , and $U(\mathbf{J})$ is the dissipation factor given by

$$U(\mathbf{J}) = \int_0^{\mathbf{J}} d\mathbf{J}' \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{J}'). \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting the power law in equation (3.5), the dissipation factor becomes

$$U(\mathbf{J}) = \frac{E_c J_c}{n+1} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{J}|}{J_c} \right)^{n+1}. \quad (3.6)$$

In 2D, you can ignore the ' $\nabla \phi$ ' term in functional F as, in the minimation method, we keep the current constraints. The functional in 2D will, thus, be

$$F(\Delta \mathbf{J}) = \int_V dV \left(\frac{1}{2} \Delta \mathbf{J} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{A}[\Delta \mathbf{J}]}{\Delta t} + \Delta \mathbf{J} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{A}_a}{\Delta t} + U(\mathbf{J}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{J}) \right). \quad (3.7)$$

The solution of this method, \mathbf{J} , at different time steps, is a minimum and it is proven to be unique [177], due to the lack of maximums and saddle points. The minimization can be computed very easily in a computer through various

Figure 3.1: Geometry of the considered strip with length l and width $2w$. (a) shows the tape in 3D, and (b) shows cross section of the tape.

algorithms like maximum gradient method, golden section search, Downhill simplex method, or Powell's method [179]. However in our group, we have developed our own minimization method, which reminds the maximum gradient method [118]. The computation can further be made faster by using sectors in the sample volume [180] and using parallel computing. This method has also been benchmarked and verified by numerous experiments and numerical methods for different cases [181], and is used for computing the results in this document, as presented in next chapters.

3.2 Electro-Magnetic modeling: Analytical method

The time constant can be understood as the time that it takes for the superconducting stack to reach $1/e$ of its original magnetization (around 37 percent), with e being the Euler number, since the application of ripple field or the start of demagnetization procedure. An approximated formula of time constant for a single tape or stack of tapes can be found analytically as follows.

3.2.1 Time constant for a single tape

A single strip, as shown in Figure 3.1, is considered for the analytical formulation of the time constant. Here, the current density is with opposite signs on each half width of the the strip.

The inductance of a conductor is given, in general, as

$$L = \frac{1}{I^2} \int dV \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{A}, \quad (3.8)$$

where, S is the cross section area of the conductor. For a thin strip of half width w centered at the origin and parallel to the x axis, the vector potential $\mathbf{A} = A\mathbf{e}_z$ is

$$A(x, y = 0) = A_{strip}(x + \frac{w}{2}, y = 0) - A_{strip}(x - \frac{w}{2}, y = 0), \quad (3.9)$$

where, for one half,

$$A_{strip}(y = 0) = \frac{\mu_0 I}{\pi w} \left(-2w + 2(x + \frac{w}{2}) \ln|x + \frac{w}{2}| - (x - \frac{w}{2}) \ln|x - \frac{w}{2}| \right), \quad (3.10)$$

where, I is the current in the tape, assumed to be uniformly distributed. Integrating the value of A on the tape, following 3.8, gives

$$L = l \frac{\mu_0}{\pi} 2 \ln 2, \quad (3.11)$$

which is independent of the tape width, with l being the tape length.

The differential equation for this problem, taking the dynamic magneto-resistance R [86] into account, is

$$2R(I)I = -L\dot{I}, \quad (3.12)$$

since the voltage drop in the closed loop for I is $V = 2RI$, and by Faraday's law $V = -L\dot{I}$. The dynamic magneto-resistance due to the transverse AC field in a slab, for B_m larger than the threshold field B_{th} [86], is

$$R = 2lfd \frac{1}{I_c} \left[B_m - B_{th}(I) \right], \quad (3.13)$$

with

$$B_{th}(I) = \mu_0 J_c \frac{d}{2} \left(1 - \frac{I}{I_c} \right), \quad (3.14)$$

where, f , and d are the frequency, and thickness of the tape, respectively.

For critical current, $I_c = J_c w d$, the resistance, R , can be re-written as

$$R = \mu_0 l f \frac{d}{w} \left[\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 + \frac{I}{J_c w d} \right], \quad (3.15)$$

with

$$B_p = \mu_0 J_c \frac{d}{2}, \quad (3.16)$$

where, B_p is the penetration field of one tape in parallel applied field, B_m is the amplitude of the applied transverse field, respectively.

Substituting R from equation (3.15) in Ohm's law for closed loop, we obtain the first order differential equation for the current I :

$$aI^2 + bI + LI\dot{I} = 0, \quad (3.17)$$

where, a and b are constants, given as

$$a = f\mu_0 \frac{2}{J_c w^2}, \quad (3.18)$$

and

$$b = 2f\mu_0 \frac{d}{w} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right). \quad (3.19)$$

If

$$\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \gg \frac{I}{J_c w d}, \quad (3.20)$$

the dynamic magneto-resistance of equation (3.15) becomes

$$2\frac{R}{l} = f\mu_0 \frac{d}{w} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right), \quad (3.21)$$

which is independent of I . In addition, as a result of (3.20), the term with a in (3.17) can be dropped. Then, the solution of $I(t)$ is

$$I(t) = I_0 e^{-\frac{bt}{L}}, \quad (3.22)$$

where, I_0 is the current at first time step and t is the current time for which $I(t)$ is being calculated.

Thus, according to equation (3.11) and (3.21), the time constant will be

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{f\pi}{\ln 2} \frac{d}{w} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right), \quad (3.23)$$

where, J_c is assumed to be constant.

Brandt [88] also finds an equation for the time constant for a a single tape considering $J(x)$ dependence, which is more accurate as it allows non-uniform J , but hard to deduce. This equation is given as

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \Lambda \frac{2\pi f d}{w} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right), \quad (3.24)$$

where, from numerical deductions, Λ is a constant equal to 0.6386, and w is the half width of the sample.

Equations (3.23) and (3.24) are both proportional to each other and specific ratio. Our formula (equation (3.23)) predicts a bit lower τ , the results for which are being compared with Brandt's formula in Section 4.1.2, and, hence, it is more pessimistic. The benefit of our deduction here is that it helps us to derive further formulas for the time constant, as seen below.

3.2.2 Time constant for a thin stack of tapes

For a thin stack with very low height, the problem can be considered similar to that of a single tape. Since now the magnetic flux on a single tape is $\phi = nLI$, with n being the number of tapes and I the current in each tape, the time constant is similar for a single tape but n times larger, and is given as

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{f\pi}{\ln 2} \frac{d}{wn} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right). \quad (3.25)$$

3.2.3 Time constant for thick stack of tapes

Similarly to the above section, the time constant for the stack of tapes can also be found. The only difference in the method is the magnetic flux crossing a tape generated by the whole stack, being

$$\phi = nMI, \quad (3.26)$$

where, n is the number of tapes in the stack, M is the mutual inductance between the stack and one tape, and I is the current in one tape.

Figure 3.2: Stack between 2 ferromagnetic blocks act as an infinite stack.

For a stack with height D , M will be

$$M = l \frac{4w}{3D} \mu_0, \quad (3.27)$$

where, $2w$ is the width of stack and l is the length. In the equation above, we assumed uniform J in each of the half stack.

The formula of M above can be found from

$$M = \frac{1}{I_{stack} l} \int dV \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{A}, \quad (3.28)$$

where, the current in the stack follows $I_{stack} = nI$. The vector potential generated by one stack with uniform current density J , and width w , is

$$\frac{A_{slab}}{\mu_0} = \begin{cases} -J_e w x, & \text{if } x \geq \frac{w}{2}, \\ -J_e (x^2 + w^2/4), & \text{if } |x| < \frac{w}{2}, \text{ and} \\ J_e w x, & \text{if } x \leq -\frac{w}{2}, \end{cases} \quad (3.29)$$

where, we assumed that the stack behaves as a homogeneous bulk of engineering current density, J_e . Then, the vector potential now follows,

$$A(x, y) = A_{slab} \left(x + \frac{w}{2}, y \right) - A_{slab} \left(x - \frac{w}{2}, y \right). \quad (3.30)$$

Using equation (3.26), the total voltage along the current loop is given as

$$V = \oint \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \dot{\phi} = -M n \dot{I}. \quad (3.31)$$

Using that $V = 2RI$, with R being the dynamic magneto-resistance, the differential equation for I is

$$2RI = -nM\dot{I}. \quad (3.32)$$

The following condition is used

$$\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \gg \frac{I}{J_c w d}, \quad (3.33)$$

which shows that, corresponding to very large applied field or very small current, the dynamic magneto-resistance does not depend on I .

Then, the solution for $I(t)$ is found to be

$$I(t) = I_0 e^{-\frac{2R}{nM}t} = I_0 e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}. \quad (3.34)$$

Thus, substituting the value of M from equation (3.27) and R from equation (3.21) into equation (3.34) gives

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{3}{2} f \frac{dh}{w^2 n} \left(\frac{B_m}{B_p} - 1 \right), \quad (3.35)$$

where, equation (3.35) is the time constant, valid for very thick stacks of tapes. Here, if ferromagnetic material is assumed to be present at both sides in the vertical direction of a finite thickness stack, the system presents itself as a stack of infinite number of tapes due to a mirror effect, and, thus, this formula for very thick stack can also be used for that case, as can be seen in Figure 3.2. This configuration is qualitatively similar to a stack in a motor with a magnetic circuit.

3.3 Electro-Thermal modeling- METEP

The Minimum Electro-Thermal Entropy Production or METEP method obtains the temperature distribution in a superconductor or normal conductor by minimizing the entropy production, which is given in the form of a functional. In METEP method, we solve the heat equation

$$p = \frac{\partial U_T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{S}, \quad (3.36)$$

where, p is the heat power generated per unit volume, t is the time, and \mathbf{S} is the heat flux, or heat power per unit surface, transmitted outside the element volume. U_T is the thermal energy per unit volume, and is given as

Figure 3.3: Sketch of the considered square superconducting sample for the thesis. Here, k is the thermal conductivity of the superconductor, and k_N is the effective thermal conductivity for the superconducting surfaces with liquid Nitrogen which is derived from convection coefficient, h (equation (3.49)).

$$U_T(T) = \int_0^T C_v(T) dT, \quad (3.37)$$

where, $C_v(T)$ is the heat capacity per unit volume and T is the temperature.

Also, the heat power transmitted, \mathbf{S} , is given as

$$\mathbf{S} = -\bar{k}\nabla T, \quad (3.38)$$

where, \bar{k} is the thermal heat conductivity tensor.

We solve this above heat diffusion equation (3.36) by minimizing the functional

$$L_T = \int dS \left[(h(T) - U_T(T_0)T) \frac{1}{\Delta t} + G(\nabla T) - q(J) \right], \quad (3.39)$$

where, T_0 is the temperature at the previous time step, $h(T)$ is equal to

$$h(T) = \int_0^T U_T(T') dT', \quad (3.40)$$

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and time t is equal to

$$t = t_0 + \Delta t, \quad (3.41)$$

where, t_0 is the time at the previous time step and Δt is the change in time from the previous time step.

Here, $G(\nabla T)$ is equal to

$$G(\nabla T) = - \int_0^{\nabla T} d\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{k}\mathbf{g}, \quad (3.42)$$

where, we assume by now that k is independent of T . Later, we will take $k(T)$ dependence iteratively by minimizing the functional, then applying $k(T)$ according to the solution of T , and continue iterating until the difference of the local T between two time steps is below a certain tolerance.

For isotropic material, G can be simply written as

$$G(\nabla T) = -\frac{1}{2}k(\nabla T)^2, \quad (3.43)$$

and, for anisotropic material with diagonal \mathbf{k} , G will be

$$G(\nabla T) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_p k_{pp} (\partial_p T)^2, \quad (3.44)$$

where, the sum in p is in all the components of the space. $p \in \{x, y, z\}$ in 3D space and $p \in \{x, y\}$ in infinitely long 2D problems.

The term $q(J)$ in equation (3.39) is the heat loss, and can be written as

$$q(J) = \int_0^T \rho(J, T') J^2 dT', \quad (3.45)$$

where, $\rho(J, T')$ is the non-linear temperature-dependant resistivity of the superconductor, which can be modeled by equation (2.56). This method is applied to a simple square geometry of superconductor, surrounded by liquid Nitrogen, as seen in Figure 3.3. For this case, we assume that the thermal conductivity at the surface between the superconductor and the liquid Nitrogen is given by an effective heat conductivity, k_N , given by the convection coefficient in liquid Nitrogen bath, as explained in next section.

3.4 Coupling of Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal models

One of the goals of this PhD is to combine the MEMEP (Section 3.1.1) and METEP (Section 3.3) methods, in a single solver, to perform an overall anal-

Figure 3.4: Schematic of the coupling process of Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal solver.

ysis of Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal properties of superconducting sample on the application of external magnetic field or current, or both. The applied field, B_a , and voltage, V , are both in sinusoidal form and takes the formulas

$$B_a = B_m \sin(2\pi f)t, \quad (3.46)$$

and

$$V = V_m \sin(2\pi f)t, \quad (3.47)$$

where, B_m , V_m , and f are the maximum magnetic field amplitude at the peak, maximum applied voltage at the peak, and frequency of the applied signal.

For this purpose, we couple both of these methods in our program, as can be seen in Figure 3.4. Both MEMEP and METEP solvers are connected through a time loop, where METEP is solved first and then MEMEP is solved, for each time step for number of cycles. The whole process is explained next.

In this solver, the critical current density, J_c , is not constant, and it is temperature dependent. This $J_c(T)$ can be taken from equation (2.55). The METEP method in Electro-Thermal solver, thus, solves for temperature, and modifies $J_c(T)$ in each element in sample mesh. Next, using this $J_c(T)$, in each element, the MEMEP method in Electro-Magnetic solver solves for current density, J , in the sample. This result, involving J , modifies the heat loss in the sample, $q(T)$, using the Power Law and normal resistivity of the sample, which are dependent on J . Thus, the new J profile of the sample is then passed on to the Electro-Thermal solver to calculate new $q(T)$ from equation (3.45), and this whole process is repeated until the difference between the

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iterations is below a certain small tolerance.

Figure 3.5: Temperature dependence of the convective heat transfer coefficient, h . Here, $T = T_{face}$, and heat transfer with liquid Nitrogen occurs as (a) Free convection, (b) nucleate boiling, (c) transition boiling, and (d) film boiling. Data provided by Dr. Frederic Sirois, Dept. of Electrical Engineering, Polytechnique Montreal [107].

In reality, the thermal conductivity, $k(T)$, and the Power Law exponent, $n(T)$, are generally temperature dependent. For simplicity at the initial stage, k and n are assumed to be constant, but the model is able to consider the variability of k and n . The superconducting sample is surrounded by liquid Nitrogen, which provides convective cooling effect to the superconducting surface following the Newton's Law of Cooling

$$Q_c = h(T_{face} - T_N)A(T_{face} - T_N), \quad (3.48)$$

where, T_{face} is the surface temperature of a face of a mesh element, A is the area of the face, and $h(T_{face} - T_N)$ is the effective non-linear steady state convection coefficient. The dependence of h on temperature change can be seen in Figure 3.5, and is explained in detail in Section 2.6.1. For the considered problem of magnetic quench in this thesis, we use the convection coefficient in the range of nucleate boiling from this curve to simulate a very efficient cooling, with a possibility to upgrade our program to consider for all these phases ((a,b,c,d) in Figure 3.5), according to the presented problem.

At the surface of the superconductor, we consider an effective thermal conductivity, k_N , which is related to the aforementioned thermal convection coefficient through

$$k_N = h \times \Delta x, \tag{3.49}$$

where, Δx is the length of 1 mesh element.

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Chapter 4

Cross-field demagnetization and trapped fields of HTS stacks

The following results have been found using the Minimum Electro Magnetic Entropy Production (MEMEP) method. Firstly, the 2D MEMEP model is benchmarked with the 3D MEMEP model, and 2D model is, thereby, used to check how demagnetization of a superconducting tape is affected by altering various state parameters. Later, a time constant study, due to the exponential decay of trapped field, is conducted to check the rate of demagnetization for different samples under the influence of various parameters. Then, the demagnetization of very thick stacks (up to 100 tapes) is presented for millions of cycles, using the DMR model. Lastly, a unique configuration of soldered stacks is considered for the case of cross field demagnetization. The computations have been performed in a computer with 64 bit Linux operating system and Intel Core i7-7700 processor with 3.60GHz x 8 logical cores and 16 GB RAM, which is able to carry out various simulations/cases simultaneously.

4.1 Modeling by Power Law $E(J)$ relation

Magnetization trends in superconducting tapes have been analyzed in this section, depending on different parameters. The thickness of the tape considered is $2 \mu m$, unless otherwise specified, and the separation between tapes is $60 \mu m$ for the stacks of tapes. The sample is first magnetized through Field Cooling process for 100 seconds, 300 mT applied field magnitude, and later it is set to be relaxed for 900 seconds. After relaxation, a demagnetizing ripple field is applied in transverse direction with high frequency of 500 Hz and peak ripple field amplitudes ranging from 2 mT to 200 mT (Figure 4.1). The magnetic field waveform is triangular in general (later sinusoidal), and it is applied for

Figure 4.1: (a) Field is applied firstly for magnetization, and then, after relaxation, transverse alternating field is applied to check demagnetization. (b) shows the directions for magnetizing (B_m) and ripple cross fields (B_r).

30 to 250 cycles, depending on the particular case. The critical current density, J_c , for the sample is considered to be 1.36×10^{10} A/m² (unless specified otherwise), corresponding to 326.4 A of critical current, and being of the same order of magnitude of standard commercial samples at 77 K self-field. The results are practically the same for triangular and sinusoidal field waveform, given the high power-law exponents that causes a similar response to that of Critical State Model. Triangular waveform here is used to simulate a constant ramp rate in each half-cycle. From this, the magnetic moment calculations and trapped field analysis has been carried out. The trapped field is calculated at an observation point located at 1 mm distance from the center of the tape in the x direction for single tapes (Figure 4.1). The decay of trapped field and magnetization is roughly the same as both are caused by the re-arrangement of current density.

4.1.1 Instantaneous dependence of the trapped field

Benchmark of 2D MEMEP model with 3D MEMEP model

A comparison is made between the 2D MEMEP model being used in this document to the 3D MEMEP model in [181]. The 3D MEMEP model is previously benchmarked with experiments and H-Formulation (in commercial software) [182], and, thus, benchmarking the considered 2D model with 3D MEMEP model is rational. All the parameters for this calculation are same, except that the 3D model uses a superconducting tape with a finite length, and the 2D model is applied to an infinitely long tape. In addition, the 2D model assumes triangular demagnetization ripple field, while the 3D model assumes sinusoidal field.

Figure 4.2: Trapped field comparison for different lengths of tape in 3D and 2D modeling, considering tape size as $10\mu\text{m} \times 12\text{mm}$, ripple field amplitude as 40 mT, 4×16 mesh, and J_c as $2.72 \times 10^9 \text{ A/m}^2$. Infinite length for the tape is considered for 2D case. Tape sizes considered for 3D modeling are 12 mm, 36 mm, and 60 mm.

Firstly, Figure 4.2 shows the entire process of demagnetization calculations. Initially, we see a gain in trapped field during the magnetization process of up to 100 seconds. Then the field is switched off (for around 900 seconds) and we reach a stable relaxation mode, where equilibrium is achieved at a bit lower trapped field value than what we achieved in magnetization process. Later, an alternating cross ripple field is applied, and a sudden drop in magnetization is seen, which we call demagnetization of the sample.

The trapped field is compared in Figure 4.2 for both 3D and 2D models. The trapped field portrays the same behavior with consistent results in both models, specially for long tapes in 3D, as the 2D case considers infinite length. This shows that there are no systemic errors in the program. Moreover, it shows that the experiments of trapped fields on samples as short as 3 times the width can be successfully modeled by 2D methods. The initial and final values of the trapped field are different in the case of tape with short length. This is because of the assumption of the infinite length of superconducting tape in 2D model. For long tapes, the 2D and 3D models also agree quantitatively.

The trapped fields during the demagnetization process can be compared in Figure 4.3, being of higher importance. For all cases, the same qualitative

Figure 4.3: Drop in trapped field (demagnetization) in 3D and 2D modeling for different tape lengths considering tape size as $10\mu\text{m} \times 12\text{mm}$, ripple field amplitude as 40 mT, 4×16 mesh, and J_c as 2.72×10^9 A/m². Infinite length for the tape is considered for 2D case. Tape sizes considered for 3D modeling are 12 mm, 36 mm, and 60 mm.

behavior of both models is obtained over the period of 10 cycles. Here, again we observe that if the tape length is 3 times or more than the tape width, the the 2D and 3D MEMEP models practically show the same results. The 3D and 2D models both show demagnetization of around 15 percent, which proves the validity of the 2D MEMEP model.

Current density

The current density profiles for a stack of 10 tapes, with each tape of thickness $2\mu\text{m}$ and width 12 mm, can be seen in Figures 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6. In the plots, we artificially expand the tape thickness in order to see the current profiles. Due to the small thickness of the tapes, the current density penetrates the stack very fast, already at the first time step, which is around 0.05 when normalized with time period of the applied field. By the end of magnetization, the stack is almost saturated (Figure 4.4 (b)), and by the end of relaxation (900 seconds) it shows some decay in magnetization (Figure 4.4 (c)).

Now, we show the case when a ripple field applied to the stack in orthonormal direction to the current density and parallel to the tape surface.

The current density penetrates the tape from the transverse side as compared to Figure 4.4 (200 mT ripple field). During the first cycle of ripple field, the current density changes signs at each peak of triangular waveform magnetic field, as can be seen in Figure 4.5. At the end of 30 cycles, a clear cross field demagnetization of the stack can be observed in Figure 4.6.

The demagnetization of a single tape can be seen in Figure 2.11. Comparing the stack with a single tape in the above figures shows that a single tape has more penetration of opposing screening currents in the sample for the same amount of cycles.

Mesh dependence

The dependence of demagnetization on the choice of mesh is analyzed for a 10 μm tape. As can be seen in Figure 4.7, the demagnetization results do depend on the meshing of the sample. The calculations require even number of meshes in both directions, as to allow full magnetization and full cross-field demagnetization of tapes so that J can reach the center of the sample. To show this, a simulation is conducted with 3x15 mesh, with 3 and 15 being the number of elements in tape thickness and tape width, respectively. It is realized that the odd-number mesh (3x15) results in big error of about 30 percent for high field amplitudes, above 100 mT. However, at smaller fields, it can be good enough for quick approximated results. Several even number of meshes in thickness and width of the sample gives closer results to each other. The 12x40 mesh, with 12 elements in thickness, and 40 elements in width, is around 5 percent away from the result produced by 24x40 mesh, and can be considered as a good mesh size for intermediately accurate results. The higher elements in width, in 24x80 mesh as compared to the 24x40 mesh, just produces around 1-2 percent of difference in results, which can be ignored when the requirement is that of faster calculations. The 24x40 mesh comes out as an optimum mesh choice, with pretty close to accurate results, and, hence, it is used widely in the numerical calculations in this document. Higher mesh sizes do provide better results, but also take higher computation times, which is a drawback of using a good mesh. The difference in results is not much though, when lower mesh is used instead of high mesh, and the important point to consider is the even-ness of the mesh. Additionally, the results show that high mesh is necessary for calculations with high number of cycles, since the numerical error accumulates at each cycle.

4.1. MODELING BY POWER LAW $E(J)$ RELATION

Figure 4.4: Current density profiles for a stack of 10 tapes, with single tape thickness $2 \mu\text{m}$, at (a) first time step at the start of magnetization (0.25 s, applied field 300 mT), (b) end of Field-Cool magnetization (single pulse), 10 seconds, and (c) end of relaxation (900 seconds). Tape thickness expanded in plot for better visibility.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.5: Current density profiles for stack of 10 tapes at (a) first positive peak of applied ripple field at the start of cross field demagnetization, (b) negative peak of applied ripple field in first cycle of demagnetization. Ripple field amplitude of 200 mT is used.

Figure 4.6: Current density profiles for a stack of 10 tapes at the end of cross field demagnetization (after 30 cycles of applied ripple field, 200 mT amplitude).

Figure 4.7: Mesh dependence for different ripple fields for a 10 μm thick tape after 30 cycles. 24 \times 40 mesh is sufficient in most cases.

Figure 4.8: Thickness dependence of trapped field for different ripple fields for 12×40 mesh, constant $J_c d$, and 30 cycles of applied ripple field.

Thickness dependence

The demagnetization of a superconducting tape also depends on its thickness. For this calculation, constant $J_c d$, or constant sheet current density, is considered. From Figure 4.8, it can be seen that the demagnetization percentage and rate increases with increase in thickness. For 100 mT, the demagnetization for 5 μm tape is about 20 percent from its initial value after relaxation. This demagnetization increases to up to 50 percent for 10 μm tape at the same field, and around 75 percent for 20 μm tape. It can also be seen here that demagnetization is dependent on ripple field amplitude. The demagnetization is higher for high amplitude of magnetic fields, with around 50 percent drop for 20 μm at 40 mT as compared to only around 6 percent drop at 10 mT. This drop rises to almost 100 percent at 200 mT for the same tape in about 30 cycles of applied ripple field. There is almost negligible change at low fields.

Ripple field dependence

Next, we analyze in detail the effect of the ripple magnetic field for up to 250 cycles (Figure 4.9). Here, the parallel penetration field for 2 μm tape is calculated to 17.1 mT (equation (3.16)). There is very low demagnetization in the tape at low ripple fields of 2 mT, 10 mT, and 17 mT, which is below the parallel penetration of the tape. Above this value, the cross magnetic field starts penetrating the sample, with dynamic magneto-resistance appearing, and, hence, demagnetization is observed. When calculated for high number of

Figure 4.9: Trapped field dependence with change in ripple field amplitude for $2\ \mu\text{m}$ tape thickness, 24×40 mesh, $1.36\times 10^{10}\ \text{A/m}^2$ J_c , and 250 cycles of applied ripple field.

cycles, it is realized that the demagnetization decay is exponential in nature for high magnetic fields above penetration field. The drop in trapped field is up to 85 percent for a $2\ \mu\text{m}$ tape at 200 mT of applied field for 250 cycles, which is just around 0.5 seconds for a 500 Hz excitation, a very small time for any practical application of this type of superconducting sample, and is, thus, an issue of major concern.

For applied ripple field amplitudes below the penetration field, the Critical State Model predictions by Brandt [88] obtain partial demagnetization, or a demagnetization to a non-zero asymptotic value. The observed negligible demagnetization could be due to the smooth E(J) relation or insufficient mesh. However, the rate of this demagnetization increases with the ripple field, as well as is dependent on the number of stacked tapes, as seen below.

Number of tapes dependence

The demagnetization of a stack also depends on the number of tapes. Figure 4.10 shows that there is less decay in a stack with high number of tapes. This is due to a larger self inductance of the magnetization currents as discussed in Section 3.2. At low fields below the parallel penetration field of considered tape (17.1 T), there is no relevant demagnetization in any of the considered cases. At higher fields, such as 150 mT, the demagnetization after 30 cycles is only about 2.5 percent for the stack of 4 tapes, as compared to 5 percent

Figure 4.10: Number of tape dependence of trapped field for different ripple fields for 24×40 mesh, $2 \mu\text{m}$ tape thickness, 30 cycles, and $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$ J_c .

of 2 tape stack and 15 percent for a single tape. This value is the worst for 200 mT, where a single tape is left with just around 62 percent of its original magnetization, as compared to 90 percent for a stack with 4 tapes. Also, as seen from Figure 4.11, the high number of tapes in a stack enables to retain trapped fields for much longer, as compared to single tape, and, thus, a stack with many tapes is preferable for practical applications of superconductors.

4.1.2 Time constant study

We define the time constant as the relaxation time when the trapped field or magnetization of a superconducting tape becomes $1/e$ times (0.37) its original value, by assuming exponential decay of trapped field, which we have also seen in previous results. A comprehensive time constant study has been carried out to check the rate of demagnetization of superconducting tapes, and its dependence on various parameters such as tape thickness and width, applied ripple field amplitude and frequency, and number of tapes in a superconducting stack. These dependencies are discussed in the following subsections. All cases that are considered here are for $2 \mu\text{m}$ tape with critical current density of $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$ at 24×40 mesh, and 200 mT of applied ripple field with 500 Hz frequency for 30 cycles, unless specified otherwise, for better comparison of different cases.

Figure 4.11: Trapped field time evolution for several number of tapes for 200 mT ripple field amplitude, $2\mu\text{m}$ tape thickness, 24×40 mesh, and 30 cycles of applied ripple field.

Thickness dependence

From Figure 4.12, it can be seen that the time constant increases with increasing the thickness but keeping J_c constant, which is in contrast to the result in Figure 4.8, where $J_c d$ is constant keeping the penetration field constant. The rate and amount of demagnetization is lower for thicker tapes, which is due to the increase of the penetration field in parallel direction. As compared to 0.11 s of time constant for 2 μm tape, a 10 μm tape has time constant of around 0.15 s, and rises to 0.22 s for 20 μm tape, which is almost double than the 2 μm tape.

Ripple field dependence

The change in ripple field also changes the time constant, with faster demagnetization for higher ripple field amplitudes (Figure 4.13). At low fields below the parallel penetration field (17.1 mT), the time constant is very high, being practically indefinite for 2 mT. The time constant for 10 mT ripple field is around 67.2 seconds. The quantity $1/\tau$ increases linearly with applied ripple field amplitude. Thus, low values of ripple field amplitudes are appreciated for slower demagnetization of a superconducting tape. In addition, amplitudes below the penetration field will reach non-zero asymptotic values [88].

Figure 4.12: Time Constant dependence with change in thickness, 200 mT ripple field amplitude, 200×10 mesh, constant J_c of 1.36×10^{10} A/m², and 30 cycles of applied ripple field.

Frequency dependence

The time constant shows almost a linear dependence of the change of frequency, experiencing a decrease in its value with increase in frequency. The different frequencies considered for this analysis are 40 Hz, 100 Hz, 250 Hz, and 500 Hz, with lowest value of time constant at 500 Hz being just 0.10 seconds. For a lower frequency like 40 Hz, this value is 1.08 seconds, around 10 times larger when compared to 500 Hz, and 2.5 times larger than the time constant at 100 Hz. Thus, the demagnetization decay rate also depends on the frequency of applied ripple field amplitude (Figure 4.14 (a)). The change in time constant per unit cycle (τ/T , T being the time period) can also be seen in Figure 4.14 (b), where it is observed that this quantity slightly increases with the frequency. The results are consistent with Baghdadi et al [15] for frequencies higher than 50 Hz.

Width dependence

The time constant increases with the tape width (Figure 4.15). The time constant for 5 mm (0.0578 seconds), is more than twice the time constant for 2 mm (0.0257 seconds), and this factor increases to up to 4 times for a 12 mm (0.1057 seconds) tape. This increase of time constant for a wider superconducting tape is due to the dynamic magneto-resistance, which depends on the width of superconducting tapes. The wider the tape, the lower the

Figure 4.13: Time Constant dependence with change in ripple field amplitude, 24×40 mesh, tape thickness of $2 \mu\text{m}$, and constant J_c of $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$.

resistance for same net current I . Therefore, the width of a HTS tape is also an important design parameter for high temperature superconductivity applications.

Number of tapes dependence

Stacks with high number of tapes can hold their magnetization for longer times than a single tape, as seen in previous Section 4.1.1. This can be proven and explained in more details by time constant analysis. As can be seen in Figures 4.16 and 4.17, the stacks with higher number of tapes can trap magnetization for a longer time, even at higher fields. At 40 mT, the time constant is 3 times in a stack of 2 tapes, and up to 5 times in a stack of 10 tapes, as compared to a single tape. At 200 mT, the time constant is relatively small for a single tape, as compared to the stack with 20 tapes. For 20 tapes, the time constant is higher than any other cases here. With increase in cross magnetic field amplitude above penetration field, there is demagnetization in each of these cases, but qualitative analysis from these graphs show that single tapes demagnetize very fast as compared to any n number of tapes in a superconducting stack.

Figure 4.14: Time Constant dependence with (a) change in frequency, and (b) change in frequency per unit cycle, using tape thickness of $2 \mu\text{m}$, 12×40 mesh, ripple field amplitude of 200 mT, 30 cycles of applied ripple field, and $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2 J_c$.

Comparison with analytical formulas

We compare the analytical models for uniform J , and Brandt's, from chapter 3 for time constant to those generated by the numerical MEMEP method used in calculations.

For a single tape, the time constant formulas as given in equations (3.25) and (3.24) are used, and their comparisons with the numerical data is shown in Figures 4.18, and 4.19, depending on different state variables such as ripple field amplitude, and frequency, respectively. It can be seen from these graphs that the time constant values for numerical analysis are very close to the data from analytical formulas. Thus, in contrast of non-uniform \mathbf{J} by Brandt, we validate the approximation of uniform \mathbf{J} in the width of the tape for our formulas. The numerical method takes non-uniform \mathbf{J} in both the thickness and width of the tape, so the agreement with numerical results approve of our assumptions. The curves for analytical data are a bit lower, in general, than the numerical results, being more pessimistic, and, hence, providing safer values for engineering applications.

Similarly, the time constant comparison between numerical and analytical results for a stack with different number of tapes is also performed, using equation (3.35) for analytical purposes. The graphs for both these results are in a very good agreement with each other, especially for higher values of ripple fields, as can be seen in Figure 4.20. Thus, we expect that all the equations

Figure 4.15: Time Constant dependence with change in width, using ripple field amplitude of 200 mT, 24×40 mesh, constant J_c of 1.36×10^{10} A/m², and 30 cycles of applied ripple field.

in Section 3.2 will be valid to predict demagnetization rates.

Here, note that the the y-axis value is the inverse of time constant for Figures 4.18 and 4.20, which shows linear increase of this quantity with ripple field amplitude and decrease in number of tapes. The relative difference between numerical and analytical method is independent of ripple field amplitudes for large enough amplitudes. The slightly weaker frequency dependence for numerical method is due to the finite power law exponent, which results in higher effective parallel penetration field due to allowance of $|\mathbf{J}|$ over J_c . The agreement is expected to get better with higher number of computed cycles since these results are calculated at very early stages of demagnetization decay curves. Also, higher Power Law exponent can bring the results closer, since at very high n values (above 100) the E-J Power Law Model comes very close to Critical State Model, which the formulas use.

Comparison of stack of tapes with bulk

A comparison has been done for the bulk of the same geometry as the size of stack of 10 tapes ($2 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, $60 \mu\text{m}$ separation), for applied ripple field amplitudes up to 400 mT. The time evolution of trapped fields for the bulk and the stack can be seen in Figures 4.21 (a) and (b), respectively. From these graphs, it is evident that the bulk demagnetizes more than the stack for fields above the penetration field, going to zero in just around 10 cycles for very high field (400 mT), and, thus, the stack is better than the bulk in this

Figure 4.16: Time Constant dependence with change in stack, using $2 \mu\text{m}$ tape thickness, 100×10 mesh, and constant J_c of $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$.

Figure 4.17: Time Constant dependence with change in stack, using $2 \mu\text{m}$ tape thickness, 100×10 mesh, and constant J_c of $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$.

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Figure 4.18: Time Constant dependence on ripple field amplitude for numerical analysis calculated at 30 cycles of applied ripple field. Numerical calculations agree with simplified formulas (equations (3.23) and (3.24)).

Figure 4.19: Time Constant dependence on ripple field frequency for numerical analysis calculated at 30 cycles of applied ripple field. Numerical calculations agree with simplified formulas (equations (3.23) and (3.24)).

Figure 4.20: Comparison of the Time Constant values for number of tapes, between numerical and analytical analysis. Numerical calculations agree with analytical formula for stack of tapes (equation (3.25)).

case. In lesser measure, this also applies for lower amplitudes. The current density profiles for the bulks on the application of 40 mT and 200 mT ripple field amplitudes can be seen in Figures 4.22 (a) and (b) respectively. When compared to the stack of 10 tapes of the same size (Figure 4.6), it is seen that the bulk demagnetizes more, showing a different current profile for same parameters. It is also observed that the time constant values are higher for a stack as compared to the bulk, which is as expected (Figure 4.23). For high ripple fields, the difference can be of several orders of magnitude. Looking at the asymptotic trapped field values in Figure 4.24, it is observed that for ripple fields below penetration field, the bulk retains some magnetization even after a large number of cycles (ideally, up to infinite), in contrast to the stack for which the magnetization goes to zero when the applied field is below the penetration field. Hence, in that manner, a bulk facing 40 mT ripple field amplitude is better than the stack of the same size and it can be used for applications requiring longer runtimes.

Implications on motor design

The time constant data and behavior found in the above sections have a great impact on superconducting magnet applications. Specifically, for motors, increasing the number of tapes in stacks up to 100, and the tape width to 40 mm, will increase the time constant by orders of magnitude. Using ferromagnetic material on opposite sides of the stack can generate a mirror effect for super-

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(a)

(b)

Figure 4.21: Normalized trapped field values for (a) bulk, and (b) stack, using 100×10 mesh. Bulk size, $12 \text{ mm} \times 0.56 \text{ mm}$, is equal to the overall stack size and engineering critical current density. 500 Hz of ripple field frequency is used here.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.22: Current density profiles for a bulk on the application of ripple field amplitudes (a) 40 mT, and (b) 200 mT, at the first peak of 30th cycle of applied ripple field, using 24×40 mesh. Same bulk size, with engineering critical current density, as the 10-tape stack is used.

Figure 4.23: The Time Constant for the stack is much higher than for the equivalent bulk (results for 100×10 mesh). Same bulk size, with engineering critical current density, as the 10-tape stack is used.

Figure 4.24: Comparison of the asymptotic trapped field values for bulk and stack for different ripple fields. Stack of 10 tapes, and same bulk size and engineering critical current density as the stack. Penetration field for the stack (around 17 mT) is lower than the bulk for Benchmark configuration.

conducting stacks, thus, increasing the time constant. Also, time constant is much higher for low ripple field magnitudes and high thicknesses, which can be kept in mind for considering the practical usage and environment around the stacks in motor. Furthermore, the analytical formulas for time constant will be very helpful for engineers for quick estimation of the real time runtimes of motors.

An important point to note from the results here is that the absolute time constant values are very less, in order of less than a second to few seconds. Practically, that means that a superconducting motor with stacks can get demagnetized by around 63 percent in a matter of seconds (for considered parameters), thus losing power output drastically. So, to find more solutions to the problem, we use DMR method from Section 4.2.1 to check the full runtime of motors, and the results are shown in next section.

4.2 Dynamic Magneto-Resistance approach

Till now, all the results are achieved by incorporating E-J Power Law in MEMEP method (let's call this E-J Power Law Model). Though the results are accurate, it takes a lot of time to calculate them, which depends on various factors such as the applied ripple field amplitude, tape/stack geometry, etc. For example, calculating demagnetization of a 10 tape stack for 100 cycles of applied ripple field may take around 1-1.5 months, depending on the amplitude. However, this method is still much powerful and faster than the conventional methods such as H-formulation and T-A formulation. Since we wrote the program in C++ and use basic Linux based compilers, it is also much faster than the commercial software.

One of the major goals of this thesis is to develop a method that can calculate millions of cycles in a relatively short time. The reason behind this is the high range of ripple field frequencies in superconducting motors, which can range in thousands of Hertz due to the ripple harmonics. Also, for 1 million cycles, the total running time for 2400 Hz frequency (as used in this work) is only around 7 minutes. Any average small distance flight is at least 2 hours, and, thus, to simulate demagnetization of superconducting stacks for the whole runtime of flights, we need to calculate demagnetization for millions of cycles of applied ripple field.

We incorporate the effective $E(J)$ relation developed using Dynamic Magneto-Resistance (DMR) into MEMEP method for this purpose (let's call this DMR Model), as defined in Section 4.2.1.

Figure 4.25: (a) The $E(J)$ relation derived from the dynamic-magneto resistance (DMR) model. (b) shows that the DMR model require only 1 element in thickness mesh for the tape which makes the calculations faster.

4.2.1 New effective $E(J)$ relation (DMR model)

Critical State Model from equation (2.7) can be approximated as the following piecewise linear $E(J)$ relation for numerical purposes:

$$E(J) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } |J| \leq J_c, \\ \rho(|J| - J_c) \frac{J}{|J|}, & \text{if } |J| > J_c, \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

where, ρ , a very large resistivity, can have the physical interpretation of a flux-flow resistivity.

For a given transport current I , the DC component of voltage, due to the dynamic magneto-resistance (from equation (2.20)), is $V_R(I) = R(I)I$. This DC component of voltage comes from the time average of the voltage in one applied-field cycle. With DC electric field, $E_R = V_R(I)/l$, where l is the length, and average current density in the cross section of the slab, J , being $J = I/(wd)$, the effective $E(J)$ relation is

$$E_R(J) = E_0 \left[\frac{B_{ra}}{B_p} - \frac{B_{th}}{B_p} \left(\frac{J}{J_c} \right) \right] \frac{J}{J_c}. \quad (4.2)$$

Here, the equation is written in normalized dimension-less quantities, with $E_0 \equiv \mu_0 f d^2 J_c$, B_p being the parallel penetration field (Equation 3.16), and threshold magnetic field being

$$B_{\text{th}}\left(\frac{J}{J_c}\right) = B_p \left(1 - \left|\frac{J}{J_c}\right|\right). \quad (4.3)$$

For effective constitutive model based on dynamic magneto-resistance (DMR), we can divide a thin film superconductor into elements across the width, with each element having tape thickness (Figure 4.25(b), right). Then these elements can each be treated as individual slabs, given their high aspect ratios and negligible mutual magnetic shielding effects of the magnetic field's parallel component [88]. Thus, combining effective relation from DMR (equation (4.2)) and Critical State Model's $E(J)$ relation (equation (4.1)), we get the effective $E(J)$ relation:

$$E(J) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } B_{ra} \leq B_{\text{th}}(J) \text{ and } |J| \leq J_c, \\ E_R(J), & \text{if } B_{ra} \geq B_{\text{th}}(J) \text{ and } |J| \leq J_c, \\ \rho(|J| - J_c) \frac{J}{|J|} + E_R(J = J_c), & \text{if } |J| \geq J_c, \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

where,

$$E_R(J = J_c) = \frac{E_0 B_{ra}}{B_p} = 2df B_{ra}. \quad (4.5)$$

From Figure 4.25(a), it can be seen that there is no DMR when B_{ra} is less than $B_{\text{th}}(J)$, and, hence, E vanishes. Also, when B_{ra} is above B_p , there exists a non-zero E for any non-zero J . It should also be noted that at $J/J_c = 1$, the graph looks constant, but in reality there exists a slight slope that accounts for flux-flow resistivity and normalized electric field for values of J greater than J_c .

For single tape, it is already shown that this kind of approach can efficiently model cross field demagnetization effects, as long as the tape is initially fully saturated due to a transverse applied field [83, 88]. We here present a more general constitutive relation that can also model cross field demagnetization of partially magnetized samples or, as long as their characteristic frequency is much smaller than the ripple field frequency, the effect of transverse applied fields simultaneously to the parallel ripple field. This model can also be easily extended to account for non uniform J_c across the tape width or a magnetic field dependent $J_c(B)$. We apply this constitutive $E(J)$ relation, hereby, to MEMEP method to calculate cross field demagnetization of tapes, stacks, and bulks, for millions of cycles of applied magnetic field.

4.2.2 Modeling configurations

For this section, we only consider the superconducting layer of the tape, and, thus, the conductivity and permeability of the other layers, such as buffer, substrate and stabilization, is assumed to be negligibly small.

For benchmarking DMR model with E-J Power Law Model, we use a 10-tape stack with individual tape thickness $2\mu\text{m}$, tape width 12 mm, and gap between tapes $60\mu\text{m}$. The critical current density used here is $1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$ at 77 K. The mesh used in Power Law Model is 200 elements in the tape thickness and 10 elements in the tape width, whereas, only 1 element is used in the thickness mesh for DMR model (40 in the width). The field application process and parameters are the same as the previous section (ripple field of 200 mT at 500 Hz), except 5 T field is used for the initial magnetization, and ripple field is applied for 100 cycles. Let's call this Benchmark configuration (Table 2.1).

The stacks used for analysis of demagnetization of high number of cycles consists of 10-100 tapes of $1.5\mu\text{m}$ thickness and 40 mm width, with $100\mu\text{m}$ gap between tapes. This tape data corresponds to the widest commercially available tape which is considered very good for trapping high magnetic fields [123]. The critical current density for this analysis is taken from American Superconductor tape data at 30 K, and is equal to $5.78 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$. The magnetization of the sample is done at 10 T for 100 tapes to make sure there is complete penetration and magnetization of the sample. Ripple field is applied at 2400 Hz frequency for millions of cycles at different amplitudes using sinusoidal waveform. The computer used is also the same as previous section. Let's call this Rotor configuration (Table 4.1).

Modeling configurations		
Parameters	Benchmark	Rotor
Tape Thickness	$2\mu\text{m}$	$1.5\mu\text{m}$
Tape Width	12 mm	40 mm
Gap	$60\mu\text{m}$	$100\mu\text{m}$
J_c	$1.36 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$	$5.78 \times 10^{10} \text{ A/m}^2$
Ripple field frequency	500 Hz	2400 Hz

Table 4.1: Different modeling configurations for calculating results with different models.

Figure 4.26: Current density profiles for a single tape under Critical State model(a,b) and DMR model(c,d) after Field Cool Magnetization and Relaxation (a,c), and 30 cycles of demagnetizing ripple field (b,d). Single element is used in the thickness for DMR model. Thickness is also artificially expanded for better analysis.

4.2.3 Benchmark of DMR model

The results of DMR model are firstly compared with the demagnetization results from Critical State Model (CSM) and E-J Power Law model, since DMR model is based on Critical State Model. Parameters from Benchmark configuration from Section 4.2.2 are used for these calculations. The current density profiles for DMR model and Critical State Model are compared in Figure 4.26. Part (a) and (b) of Figure 4.26 shows demagnetization of the tape under Critical State Model, whereas in (b), we see the typical S-shape of current density profile after 30 cycles of applied ripple field. Part (c) and (d) of Figure 4.26 shows demagnetization under DMR model. Here, only 1 element is used in thickness mesh, and, hence, the current density is uniform along the x-axis. Comparatively, in y-axis, you can see some considerable and non-uniform demagnetization of the tape. In contrast, CSM uses 24 elements in thickness mesh, and demagnetization is more clearly visible in x-axis. The thickness average of the current density is the same for both CSM and DMR models. Since the tape is very thin, the magnetic field that they generate outside the tape is the same.

Figure 4.27 shows trapped field decay profile comparison of DMR model with CSM and E-J Power Law Model. Figure 4.27(a) shows the complete process with initial magnetization and relaxation, and later the demagnetization on the application of ripple field is graphed. Here, it can be seen that E-J Power Law model shows considerable decay during relaxation, in contrast to CSM and DMR model. The reason behind this is the frequency independence of the electro-magnetic response of the CSM, and the DMR model is identical to the CSM model when there are no applied ripple fields. Figure 4.27(b) shows the demagnetization of the tape for 30 cycles of applied rippled field. Here, we get very good quantitative agreement between all three models for single tape demagnetization.

Next, we benchmark DMR model with E-J Power Law model by checking the demagnetization behavior of a 10-tape stack by both models in Figure 4.28. In the (a) part of this Figure, you can see that DMR model shows very good agreement with E-J Power Law model, even for higher number of cycles (100). A little difference (around 0.01 percent) between both models is expected due to the DMR model being based on Critical State Model. Figure 4.28(b) shows the current density profile of the 10-tape stack after 100 cycles of demagnetization at 200 mT, and it can be confirmed that there is some demagnetization in the sample.

There are 2 major advantages of DMR model over E-J Power Law model. Firstly, the mesh used in the thickness of tapes in HTS stacks include only one element in DMR model, in contrast to the E-J Power Law model where

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.27: Trapped field decay comparison for DMR model, Critical State Model (CSM), and E-J Power Law Model.(a) shows complete trapped field curves, whereas (b) shows just the demagnetization part when ripple field is applied later. DMR model shows good agreement with other two models.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 4.28: Trapped field decay comparison for DMR model, and E-J Power Law Model, for a 10-tape stack. (a) shows demagnetization when ripple field is applied for 100 cycles and good agreement between both models. (b) shows current density profile for DMR model at 100 cycles for the 10-tape stack.

you need atleast 20 elements. The width of the tapes can have same number of mesh elements in both models. Due to this, the calculations by DMR model are very fast. Secondly, the electric field in DMR model is calculated for one whole cycle (or several cycles) of applied ripple field, whereas, the E-J Power Law model requires to calculate the electric field for every time step of applied field. We generally use 20 time steps in each cycle for E-J Power Law model. Thanks to this, you can calculate demagnetization for very high number of cycles using DMR model fairly quickly. For benchmarking, E-J Power Law model takes 1-2 months for calculating 100 cycles for a 10 tape stack (we use very high number of elements in a tape thickness mesh, i.e., up to 200 elements in 2 μm tape), depending on the applied ripple field amplitude (more time for low amplitudes). For the same case, DMR model takes only around 2 minutes to calculate 100 cycles of demagnetization. The results from this section show that the output from both models also match very accurately. This shows that the DMR model is very strong and fast when compared to its contemporary. Here, an important thing to note is that, since there is no relaxation in trapped field in DMR model (Fig. 4.27 (a)), demagnetization starts at a higher value when compared with E-J Power Law model. The latter is a more realistic model since relaxation is observed during this whole demagnetization process. Thus, if the goal is to check the absolute values for the demagnetization, E-J Power Law can be used. Otherwise, if the goal is to see the relative decrease of the trapped field, DMR model can be used. Since we compare the normalized values of trapped field in both models, the initial trapped field is not important. The most accurate results can be obtained by calculating magnetization and demagnetization by DMR and then renormalizing the trapped field by that obtained by the E-J Power Law.

4.2.4 Demagnetization of 10 tape stack and asymptotic values

Using these advantages of DMR model, we apply it to calculate demagnetization for 100 thousand cycles of ripple field for a 10-tape stack, this time using Rotor configuration. Figure 4.29 (a) shows the current density profile of the stack at 30 mT, from which it can be seen through color map that there is around 50 percent demagnetization in the stack (originally it starts with J/J_c as 1 and -1). An interesting result can be seen in Figure 4.29 (b) that the trapped field curves at low amplitudes do not decay towards full demagnetization but tend to reach an asymptotic value, whereas the curves at higher amplitude demagnetize to almost zero.

This behavior is due to the fact that the dynamic magneto-resistance,

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Figure 4.29: (a) Current density profile for 10 tape stack using Rotor configuration at 100,000 cycles of 30 mT applied ripple field. (b) shows that asymptotic values are reached for ripple field amplitudes below the tape's penetration field, 55 mT.

which is the cause of demagnetization, is dependent on the tape's threshold field, as can be seen in equation (2.20), which in turn is related to the tape's parallel penetration field (equation (4.3)). The threshold field increases with decrease in current density, J , which happens during demagnetization. After some cycles, for low amplitudes, this threshold field becomes relatively very high, in comparison to the ripple field amplitude, that makes the dynamic magneto-resistance practically zero (equation (2.20)). Hence, there is almost no demagnetization at this point and we see permanent asymptotic values, which means that the tape can stay magnetized at these values practically indefinitely. For high ripple field amplitudes over penetration field, threshold field can never overcome the field amplitude, and the dynamic magneto-resistance cannot reach zero, which makes the tape/stack fully demagnetized.

Here, the tape's parallel penetration field is around 55 mT. So from this we deduce that, if the applied ripple field amplitude is below the tape's penetration field, we get asymptotic or permanent values of trapped field, whereas, if the applied ripple field amplitude is above the parallel penetration field then the sample tends to fully demagnetize.

4.2.5 Demagnetization of 100 tape stack for millions of cycles

Now, since we have shown that the DMR model is accurate and can present asymptotic values at high number of cycles, we apply the model to a 100 tape stack for high number of applied ripple field cycles. Rotor configuration is used in this section. In real life applications, such as superconducting motors for aircraft, generally 50 to 100 tape thick stacks are used in the rotor, and, thus, modeling such thick stacks is required.

Current density profiles

Firstly, the current density profiles for the 100 tape stack can be seen in Figure 4.30. In order to observe profiles for the case that reaches asymptotic values for trapped field, 30 mT ripple field amplitude is considered for these graphs, as it is below the parallel penetration field of a tape in the stack (around 55 mT). The current density profile after relaxation in (a) shows a completely saturated, and uniform stack. After 100 thousand cycles in (b), some demagnetization is observed in the stack. From (c), it can be seen that even after applying ripple field for 2 million cycles, the stack is not fully demagnetized (where the current density is still around 50 percent of J_c), and, hence, a permanent magnetization is retained. Also, the change is not visible

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(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4.30: Current density profile for 100 tape stack using Rotor configuration at (a) post-relaxation, (b) 100 thousand cycles, and (c) 2 million cycles.

here in the thickness of the stack as we only use 1 element in the thickness of the tape. However, the non-uniformity of the current density can be observed in the width of the sample.

Demagnetization at 2 million cycles

Corresponding to Figure 4.30, we also check the trapped field curves for the 100-tape stack demagnetization under Rotor configuration. In Figure 4.31 (a), we can see that the stack demagnetizes under all ripple field amplitudes, but no asymptotic behavior can be seen for any of these curves. Thus, to check if any of these curves reach an asymptotic values, we let the calculations run for 2 million cycles. In Figure 4.31 (b), we again notice the behavior that the curves for 15 mT and 30 mT applied ripple field amplitudes reach an asymptotic value, whereas, the other curves demagnetize fully in less than 1 million cycles. Here, we again show that if the ripple field amplitude is below parallel penetration field of a tape, then the trapped field reaches an asymptotic value and some magnetization is retained permanently.

Another point to note here is that when you compare the demagnetization curves or asymptotes from Figure 4.29 to Figure 4.31, we see that the asymptotic values are same in both cases (10 tapes and 100 tapes) for the same ripple field amplitudes. This is due to the fact that the asymptotic value of the trapped field is independent of the number of tapes, and only depends on the parallel penetration field of tape and ripple field amplitude. Increasing number of tapes only slows down the demagnetization process, which increases the number of cycles required to reach the asymptotic value.

The time taken for calculating 2 million cycles of demagnetization of the 100 tape stack is around 2-4 days, depending on field amplitude, which again shows that the DMR model is very fast when compared to commercial software and E-J Power Law model.

4.2.6 Bulk vs Stack

Next, the DMR model is applied to an interesting case of bulks, to compare their demagnetization with stacks for high number of cycles. For this purpose, a 10 tape stack under Rotor configuration parameters is used. Equivalent bulk dimensions are the same as that of the stack, and engineering critical current density, which is the same as total current density per unit volume) is used for the bulk, which corresponds to

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(a)

(b)

Figure 4.31: Demagnetization of the 100 tape stack using Rotor configuration for (a) 100 thousand cycles, and (b) 2 million cycles.

$$J_{ce} = J_c n_t d \frac{1}{D}, \quad (4.6)$$

where, n_t , d , and D are the number of tapes in the stack, thickness of superconducting layer in a tape, and total height of the stack, respectively.

From Figure 4.32, a very striking contrast between the behaviors of bulks and stacks can be observed. Firstly, in Figure 4.32 (a), we observe that the stacks, even for high field amplitudes of 1 T, are not much demagnetized (almost negligible) for around 15 cycles, whereas for the same number of cycles, bulks are comparatively more demagnetized. For high amplitudes, like 1 T, bulk's trapped field even goes to zero in a very short time. But if we look at Figure 4.32 (b), we see that even bulks 'seemed' to lose much of their magnetization early, if we let the calculations running for high number of cycles, their trapped field reach asymptotic values. On the other hand, stacks for high number of cycles get more demagnetized for high number of cycles for same applied field amplitude.

Here, the stack's penetration field is 55 mT and bulk's penetration field is around 530 mT, as can be seen in Figure 4.33. This is the reason that the considered bulk and stack behave in such a way, as bulks have much higher parallel penetration field as compared to the stacks, so bulks have much higher range of ripple field amplitudes for which they can reach an asymptotic value. In other words, bulks can retain magnetization permanently for ripple field amplitudes higher than the stack's penetration field, and for these fields, stacks get fully demagnetized.

One more interesting observation here is that if the calculations are for low number of cycles, stacks get less demagnetized than bulk. So if a superconducting motor's application involves less number of cycles, or low frequencies (bigger time cycles), stacks can be used. Using stacks in such cases can be beneficial as well, as they have other advantages over bulks such as ease and flexibility of geometrical construction, and maintenance. On the other hand, if the application involves high number of cycles and high frequencies, bulks can be considered in building such motors, as they can reach stable asymptotic values faster than the stack, and for higher amplitudes as well.

4.3 Soldered stacks

Though we know now that bulks can retain more magnetization than stacks, an important point to note is that constructing a bulk is more complicated than building a stack. The fabrication processes, such as melt processing techniques, to construct an HTS bulk can be very complicated [183]. Specially,

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(a)

(b)

Figure 4.32: Comparison of bulk and stack for (a) low number of cycles, and (b) high number of cycles.

(a)

Figure 4.33: Asymptotic fields for stacks and bulks of same parameter. Penetration field of stack (around 55 mT) is lower than the same for bulk for Rotor configuration.

since we are considering bulks of the comparative size of 50-100 tapes, the problem becomes more strenuous. On the other hand, stacks have multiple benefits over a bulk. Stacks of tapes can be potentially larger in size since their length is not limited. For the same width, a long stack traps a larger magnetic flux than the equivalent array of rectangular bulks of the same engineering current density. Also, the physical properties of stacks can be tailored by interlaying other materials between the tapes. For example, including copper between tapes increases thermal conductivity, stainless steel improves mechanical strength, and soft magnetic materials can increase trapped field. In addition to that, state-of-the-art large stack of tapes present higher engineering current density than state-of-the-art large bulks. Thus, a good alternative for using bulk for the cross field demagnetization problem can be a fully soldered stack, which acts like a bulk, in order to have the best of both cases.

Here, we consider soldered stacks where HTS tapes are fully soldered in pairs on the side with the superconducting layer, as can be seen in Fig. 4.34 (a). Soldering tapes together allows for the screening currents to pass between the tapes, but it also introduces a resistance between them. For a soldered stack to act as a bulk, this resistance should be very low. Firstly, we calculate the case of a 2-tape soldered stack here, as shown in Fig. 4.34 (a). For this purpose, we have taken the ripple field frequency as 500 Hz and amplitude as 25 mT, length of the sample as 140 mm, tape width as 4 mm, tape thickness

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Figure 4.34: (a) Real soldered stack. (b) shows our modeling assumption that the tapes are soldered only at edges.

as $2 \mu\text{m}$, tape's critical current as 160 A, and the joint resistance per unit area as $380 \text{ n}\Omega \text{ per cm}^2$, which is measured in our lab. The soldered tape with this resistance acts the same as the fully coupled case, as described in [184, 185] for a 5-tape stack. E-J Power Law model is used for the soldered cases, and DMR model is used for the isolated (uncoupled) cases.

For modeling, we have assumed that all coupling current flows at the end resistance (or the soldering is only at the edges) [184], and a sketch of the configuration can be seen in Fig. 4.34 (b). As seen in Fig 4.35, this resistance is very low, and the trapped field decay for the soldered stack is the same as the decay for the partially coupled stack (modeling assumption). Here, we can also see that the soldered stack demagnetizes less than the isolated tape stack (we consider same parameters for this calculation as well). This proves our theory that soldered stacks, which acts as bulks at low enough resistances, demagnetize less than isolated stacks.

The current density profiles for the above uncoupled/isolated stack (with no soldering) and the two-tape soldered stack can be seen in Figure 4.36 (a,c,e) and Figure 4.36 (b, d, f) respectively. Figure 4.36 (a) and (b) show the fully saturated stack after the magnetization for both cases. On application of cross field for 100 cycles, the opposing screening currents penetrate from the edges for both cases, as can be seen in Figure 4.36 (c) and (d). We see the typical 'S' curve of demagnetization for the isolated stack. Comparatively, for the soldered stack, we see more penetration of the opposing screening currents due to the applied ripple field. The screening currents penetrates further

Figure 4.35: Trapped field comparison of the 2-tape stacks at 25 mT applied ripple field. Demagnetization in the partially coupled stacks (our assumption, 0Ω per cm^2) is comparable to the fully soldered stacks ($380 \text{ n}\Omega$ per cm^2), which shows that our assumption is good for the considered calculations.

in, on application of 1000 cycles of the cross field, and weakens the current density profile of the isolated stack further (Figure 4.36 (e)). Same occurs for the soldered stack as well (Figure 4.36 (f)), but in a much lower measure because the trapped field is nearing the stable asymptotic field at this point (Figure 4.35). The benefit of using a soldered stacks comes into light here, as it can be seen that the center of the sample is shielded from the cross fields, and still retain the currents that create magnetization in the x direction, as compared to the isolated stack where the demagnetizing screening currents have penetrated almost till the center.

In contrast to this, the currents fully penetrate to the center at 1000 cycles of 60 mT applied field, as can be seen in Figure 4.37 (a) and (b) for both isolated and soldered stack. This behavior is due to the reason that the applied field of 60 mT is higher than the parallel penetration field of both stacks (around 48 mT for soldered stack and 24 mT for isolated stack), and, thus, the stacks demagnetize faster when compared to the previous case of 25 mT.

Next, we calculate the demagnetization of a stack of a different construction, where the soldered tapes are arranged in 4 pairs to give a 8-tape soldered-isolated stack, as seen in Figure 4.38. The parameters for this stack are same as the previous 2-tape soldered stack. The demagnetization curves of the soldered stacks and the isolated stacks are calculated using E-J Power Law model and DMR model respectively. Adding more tapes in the stack increases the total trapped field of the sample, and lessens the demagnetization rate, as

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Figure 4.36: Current density profiles for the two tape isolated and soldered stack respectively at (a,b) Relaxation, (c,d) 100 cycles, and (e,f) 1000 cycles. Applied cross field is 25 mT. The currents penetrate from horizontal edges, shielding the area in the center.

Figure 4.37: Current density profiles at 1000 cycles, 60 mT applied ripple field, for the 2-tape (a) isolated stack and (b) soldered stack.

Figure 4.38: (a) Considered configuration of 8 tape stack, which consists of 4 pairs of 2-tape soldered stacks.

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discussed in Section 4.1.1. For the considered parameters, the parallel penetration field for 1 tape is 24 mT, whereas, the same for the 2-tape soldered stack is almost 48 mT. This means that, just like bulks, soldered stacks in pairs can withstand much higher ripple fields than isolated stacks (almost double). The current profiles of the stack in Fig 4.39 (a) and (b) show that the opposing screening currents (due to the application of cross fields) penetrate from the edges in fully saturated stacks. Here, the center region is again shielded for the individual stacks, and they retain magnetization.

Due to higher penetration fields, the soldered stacks also reach permanent asymptotic fields for cross field amplitudes below their penetration field, as can be seen in Fig. 4.40. For instance, the case of 25 mT is of interest here, as this amplitude is above the penetration field of the isolated stack but lower than the same for soldered stack. Thus, for this case, the soldered stack reaches asymptotic values after 2000 cycles, but isolated stack continues to demagnetize (till zero, if the calculations are continued). For 60 mT, both stacks demagnetize to zero since the cross field amplitude is above both of their respective penetration fields. This comparative behavior is the same as the one for the 'Bulk vs Stack' case in Section 4.2.6. Thus, we show here that the soldered stacks behave as bulk, and, to avoid rapid demagnetization like isolated stacks, soldered stacks can be used in concerned applications.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.39: (a) and (b) show current profiles of the 8-tape soldered stack after relaxation and application of 6000 cycles of cross field, respectively. The centers of the stacks are shielded from the opposing currents, and retain magnetization.

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Figure 4.40: Comparison of trapped field curves of 8-tape soldered stacks and isolated stacks. Soldered stacks demagnetize less than isolated stacks due to higher penetration fields.

Chapter 5

Coupled Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal model

We have developed a novel and fast software in C++ which performs coupled Electro-Magnetic (EM) and Electro-Thermal (ET) analysis of superconductors. In the initial stages of development, we have applied this program to the problem of electro-thermal quench, as a proof-of-concept. The quench can occur due to high input voltages and/or applied magnetic field, and, thus, our software is made capable of taking both of these parameters as inputs. The software uses the variational methods MEMEP, with E-J Power Law (Section 3.1.1), and METEP (Section 3.3), which are coupled together to give an overall analysis of the physics of electro-thermal quench. A detailed explanation of how this coupled software works, and the background physics involved, is given in Section 3.4.

For this analysis, a long superconducting bar with square cross-section of dimensions $1\text{ cm} \times 1\text{ cm}$ is considered. The sample is surrounded by liquid Nitrogen to account for the cooling effect, as can be seen in Figure 3.3. The boiling point or temperature of liquid Nitrogen is taken as 77 K. The critical temperature (T_c) and the critical current density (J_c) of the superconductor are taken as 92 K and $1 \times 10^8\text{ A/m}^2$, which are in the range of typical characteristic values of REBCO bulk superconductors. This J_c is also considered as the critical current density at 77 K, $J_{c,N}$, and is used to normalize current density profiles in this chapter. The thermal conductivity (k) and the thermal heat capacity at constant volume (C_v) of the superconductor are taken as 9 W/m.K and $9 \times 10^{-5}\text{ J/m}^3/\text{K}$, respectively, for REBCO superconductor [102,107]. For the heat exchange at the boundaries of superconductor with liquid Nitrogen, the convection coefficient, h , in the nucleate boiling region ($10000\text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$) is taken (Figure 3.5), to simulate highly efficient cooling of superconductor. Thus, a physical effective thermal conductivity, k_N , is con-

sidered at the surfaces, calculated using equation (3.49). The normal state resistivity and Power-Law exponent (n) are taken as $3 \times 10^{-7} \Omega\text{m}$ and 30, respectively. An important point to note here is that n and C_v are temperature dependant, which the software is capable of considering, and the constant values are only taken here for the sake of simplicity.

Additionally, the sinusoidal input voltages and magnetic fields are applied at 50 Hz frequency, with 20 time steps per cycle. The mesh needs to be fine for EM analysis, as the current density, J , can switch its sign in just 1 element from the surface. Since the temperature distribution does not have such discontinuities, the mesh for ET analysis can be a bit coarse. From our studies, the mesh of 30 x 30 elements is found to provide very accurate results, with minimal numerical errors, which is considered for the square bar geometry and EM/ET calculations. Initially, for the first time step, the temperature of the sample is at 77 K and the current density is zero everywhere.

The structure of this chapter is as follows. Firstly, the quench modeling of the superconductor with different input voltages is done. Here, initially we have considered the adiabatic case for the superconductor, where there is no exchange with external liquid Nitrogen. The results are compared with the Cooling enabled case, where there is heat exchange with liquid Nitrogen using the physical convection coefficient, h . Lastly, the quench modeling with considering only applied field as an input is performed.

5.1 Quench modeling with voltage input

In this section, the quench modeling for the considered superconductor is done using only voltage as an input parameter, where the applied magnetic field is zero. The EM and ET models are coupled with each other so that for each time step J from the EM model is transferred to the ET model, and T from the ET is transferred to the EM part. These two models influence each other as discussed in Section 3.4. For this purpose, the following two cases are considered for comparison.

5.1.1 Adiabatic case

Firstly, the adiabatic cases, with input peak voltages, V_m , of 1 V and 5 V, are considered. The temperature profiles and current density profiles for the voltage 1 V/m, for adiabatic case, are in Figures 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3, which we discuss below.

For the first cycle of the applied voltage, the screening current starts penetrating from the edges (Figure 5.1 (b)). The voltage of 1 V/m is considerably high, and, thus, some elements at the edges of the sample overcome the critical current density in just 3 time steps, which starts heating up the sample from the corners and the edges (Figure 5.1 (a)). At the 5th time step, or at the positive peak of applied voltage signal, the current density penetrates further into the sample, with some more temperature rise in the sample (Figures 5.1 (c) and (d)). With reducing voltage, from the peak to half cycle (zero), the current density penetrates farther towards the center of the sample, but with lower magnitude (Figure 5.1 (f)), and the temperature has risen a bit higher (Figure 5.1 (e)). Here it can be seen that the current density is zero in a major part of the center, and all current passes through the edges of the sample, which is the characteristic current density profile of a superconducting sample for the case of applied input voltage or applied input current. There is some temperature rise due to this penetrated current density (where it is higher than J_c), but the temperature rise does not affect the current density profile (or forces a negligible change), the reason being a very small rise in the temperature (to the 2nd or 3rd decimal of the temperature value).

After the half cycle, of the first cycle, the voltage with negative signal is applied, which results in the penetration of screening currents of opposite sign from the edges of the sample (Figure 5.2 (b)). This almost does not raise the temperature of the sample from the previous values (Figure 5.2 (a)). At the end of the first cycle, the currents with negative sign penetrate further into the sample, correspondingly increasing the temperature (Figures 5.2 (c) and (d)). Here, it can be seen that the negative currents do not penetrate till the same point as the positive currents did. This feature or ‘delay’ is due to the already present positive currents in the region, and, thus, it takes double voltage to completely flip the sign to the opposite values (first to zero, and then to negative). For the second cycle, this whole process repeats, and the temperature is risen more, though very minimally (below 0.1 K), which does not cause much change to the current density profile (Figures 5.2 (e) and (f)).

After running the program for 250 cycles, the current density profile and the temperature profile still look almost the same as the 1st cycle, which is due to the low voltage input (1 V/m) (Figures 5.3 (a) and (b)), although, now the maximum temperature rise is up to around 0.9 K. In contrast to this, when a higher voltage of 5 V/m is applied, we see a very high temperature rise (Figure 5.3 (c)). Since there is no cooling considered in this adiabatic case, the generated heat remains within the sample, and all elements are at a temperature much higher than the critical temperature (T_c). The high voltage induces screening currents rapidly into the sample, which generate a very high loss ($\rho(J, T)J^2$), and causes the high rise of the temperature that we observe here. This high temperature drives the superconductor into normal state,

5.1. QUENCH MODELING WITH VOLTAGE INPUT

Figure 5.1: Temperature (a,c,e) and current density (b,d,f) profiles for 1 V/m V_m , adiabatic case, at the (a,b) 3rd time step ($V/V_m = 0.6$), (c,d) positive peak, and (e,f) at the half cycle ($V = 0$), of the 1st cycle, respectively.

Figure 5.2: Temperature (a,c,e) and current density (b,d,f) profiles for 1 V/m V_m , adiabatic case, at the (a,b) negative peak of first cycle, (c,d) first complete cycle, and (e,f) at the end of the 2nd cycle, respectively.

5.1. QUENCH MODELING WITH VOLTAGE INPUT

Figure 5.3: Temperature (a,c) and current density (b,d) profiles for the adiabatic case, at the 250th cycle, taking V_m as (a,b) 1 V/m, and (c,d) 5 V/m, respectively.

with a very high resistivity, and, hence, low overall current density, as can be seen in Figure 5.3 (d). Due to high temperature, and the achievement of a normal state, the superconducting sample is now classified as quenched, which can completely destroy the sample if the temperature rise is high enough.

5.1.2 Cooling enabled case

The quenching of the magnet is a serious problem, and, hence, highly effective cooling conditions and other methods are required to overcome this potentially destructive phase. Figure 5.4 (a) and (c) show the rise in average temperature for voltage inputs of amplitude 1 V/m and 5 V/m. For 1 V/m, the temperature rise is not big, which is easily overcome by enabling cooling at the surfaces. The low temperatures also do not affect the total current in the sample, and, thus, the total current stays almost the same for the cooling

enabled case as well (Figure 5.4 (b)). Contrastingly, for 5 V/m, the average temperature rises very rapidly to above 300 K in just 250 cycles for the adiabatic case. However, with heat exchange with liquid Nitrogen in the cooling enabled case, the average temperature is limited to only around 100 K (just a bit higher than the critical temperature, 92 K), as can be seen in Figure 5.4 (c). This also affects the total current in the sample, and as observed in Figure 5.4 (d), significantly higher total current is retained for the cooling enabled case. This is because of smaller increase in resistivity in cooling enabled case, as compared to the adiabatic case, which allows for higher retention of superconducting currents. Another interesting effect observed here is that, after an initial transient, the temperature rise shows a linear behaviour for both cases, which is due to the constant C_v .

For the cooling enabled case, we analyze various curves of average temperature for different voltage inputs in Figure 5.5. Here, we can see almost no change for voltage amplitudes of 1 V/m and 2 V/m due to effective cooling. For cooling enabled case for 1 V/m, the temperature and current density profiles are presented in Figures 5.8 (a) and (b), respectively. These profiles are almost the same as for the adiabatic case (Figures 5.3 (a) and (b)), with a bit smaller range for temperature due to cooling. Thus, it is safe to assume that the current density and temperature profiles for 2 V/m input voltage will look mostly the same as for the 1 V/m. The curves for 10 V/m and 20 V/m amplitudes are for highly limiting case and, with cooling enabled, they reach a stationary state. It is interesting to note here that, even for a very high voltage like 20 V/m, the average temperature reaches a stationary state of around 325 K, which is similar to the average temperature of adiabatic case of 5 V/m (4 times less than 20 V/m) at 250 cycles. Thus, it shows the positive benefit of employing strong cooling mechanisms, as it enables operating at much higher voltage limiting in superconductors.

The case of 5 V/m with enabled cooling is of special interest, as it still shows relatively high total current (around 3000 A in Figure 5.4(d)), even though the corresponding transient state of average temperature (around 100 K) is above the critical temperature, 92 K (Figure 5.5). This effect can be understood by observing the current density and temperature profiles in Figures 5.6, 5.7, and 5.8. Firstly, in Figure 5.6 (a-d), we see that most of the sample is already fully saturated, with current densities almost 1.4 times higher than J_c , in just 5 timesteps (positive peak of 1st voltage cycle). By the half cycle, the average temperature everywhere in the sample exceeds the boiling point of liquid Nitrogen, which reduces the current density drastically (Figure 5.6 (e)). Here, only few remaining elements in the corner of the sample are around or higher than the value of J_c at 77 K, $J_{c,N}$, with J at the rest being well below $J_{c,N}$ (Figure 5.6 (f)). However, the temperature is still below T_c everywhere, and, hence, the sample remains fully superconducting.

5.1. QUENCH MODELING WITH VOLTAGE INPUT

Figure 5.4: Average temperature and total current comparison for the adiabatic case and the cooling enabled case, respectively, taking V_m as (a,b) 1 V/m, and (c,d) 5 V/m, respectively. At high applied voltages, the superconductor quenches faster, which reduces the total current in the sample rapidly.

Figure 5.5: Average temperature comparison, for different input voltages, for the cooling enabled case.

By the end of the 1st cycle (Figures 5.7 (a)-(d)), the temperatures in the middle section of the sample have risen a bit higher (to around 88 K), and the current densities at the center are almost zero. The edges still show much higher current densities, as compared to the center. This could be due to the edges being in direct contact with liquid Nitrogen, which keeps the edges at comparatively colder temperatures than the center, resulting in higher current densities as well. This effect carries on to the second cycle too, with a bit higher temperature rise in the center, but the edges being well below the critical temperature and in the range of critical current densities (Figures 5.7 (e) and (f)).

The temperature reaches the stable transient state at around 50 cycles for the input voltage of 5 V/m (Figure 5.5). On letting the program run for 250 cycles, we see that the center of the sample has much higher temperature (around 110 K) than the critical temperature (92 K), which shows that the center of sample is in the normal state (Figure 5.8 (c)). Interestingly, the edges, and some elements near the edges, show temperatures below the critical temperature. Similarly, as can be seen in Figure 5.8 (d), the edges, and some elements extending from the edges, show high current densities in the range of $J_{c,N}$. This explains the obtained total current curve in Figure 5.4(d), as most of the sample is behaving as a normal conductor but the edges present superconducting behavior, enabling high transfer of currents, given the non-linear nature of superconductors. This shows another feature of using an effective cooling mechanism, that even after achieving normal state in most

5.1. QUENCH MODELING WITH VOLTAGE INPUT

Figure 5.6: Temperature (a,c,e) and current density (b,d,f) profiles taking V_m as 5 V/m, for the cooling enabled case, at the (a,b) 3rd time step ($V/V_m = 0.6$), (c,d) positive peak, and (e,f) at the half cycle ($V = 0$), of the 1st cycle, respectively.

Figure 5.7: Temperature (a,c,e) and current density (b,d,f) profiles taking V_m as 5 V/m, cooling enabled case, at the (a,b) negative peak of first cycle, (c,d) first complete cycle, and (e,f) at the end of the 2nd cycle, respectively.

Figure 5.8: Temperature (a,c) and current density (b,d) profiles for the cooling enabled case, at the 250th cycle, taking V_m as (a,b) 1 V/m, and (c,d) 5 V/m, respectively.

of the sample at high voltages, a good amount of current is still transmitted in superconducting state in a potent cryogenic environment.

5.2 Quench modeling with applied field input

The coupled Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal model is also able to take applied magnetic field as an input. For this case, we have used input voltage as zero and cooling is enabled. The sinusoidal magnetic field is applied in y direction (Figures 5.10, 5.11, and 5.12).

Firstly, we see the average temperature curves for different applied magnetic field inputs in Figure 5.9. For the applied field of 200 mT, the maximum temperature rise from 77 K is quite small and stable during the whole process.

Figure 5.9: Average temperature curves for different applied magnetic field as input. The program is also able to take applied magnetic field as an independent input.

There is higher temperature rise for 500 mT. A cyclical rise in temperature is seen for 1 T and 2 T applied field, which is due to cyclic AC power loss generation. It is also seen here that very high fields are required (up to 5 T) to raise the temperature above critical temperature, the reason being very efficient cooling of liquid Nitrogen ($h = 10000 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$). An important point to note here is that the total current for the sample will be zero in all these cases, due to the symmetrical nature of current density penetration, which is in contrast to the case of using voltage as an input parameter in the previous section.

Next, the temperature and current density profiles for 500 mT input are analyzed. Figures 5.10 (a) and (b) show, that in just 1 time step, the screening currents start penetrating from the edges inwards. Their sign follows the right-hand rule in order to generate a high magnetic field in the y direction at the sample center. The temperature change is negligible at this stage. At the positive peak of first cycle, the currents have penetrated further into the sample, and we see some increase in temperature in the horizontal axis (Figures 5.10 (c) and (d)). On reducing the applied magnetic field to zero when reaching half cycle, the penetrating screening currents switch their sign (Figures 5.10 (e) and (f)). This can be understood from the Critical State Model, as discussed in Figure 2.5 in Section 2.2. Due to this penetration, there appears local heat generation, and, hence, the temperature of the sample rises more.

5.2. QUENCH MODELING WITH APPLIED FIELD INPUT

Figure 5.10: Temperature (a,c,e) and current density (b,d,f) profiles for applied field, B_m , of 500 mT, cooling enabled case, at the (a,b) 1st time step ($B_a/B_m = 0.2$), (c,d) positive peak, and (e,f) at the half cycle (applied field $B_a = 0$), of the 1st cycle, respectively.

The current density penetration advances towards the center while the applied magnetic field reaches its negative peak for the first cycle (Figure 5.11 (b)). Here, the central region has a small area with very low to zero current density. This is due to the relatively low amplitude of applied field input, 500 mT. At higher field inputs, the sample would get fully saturated, as we have seen for several cases in Chapter 4. At the end of 1st cycle (Figure 5.11 (d)), the penetrated screening currents again switches signs. Since the temperature rise is minimal (change in just 1st decimal figure), as can be seen in Figures 5.11 (a) and (c), the current density profiles are not much affected. This whole process repeats again for the 2nd cycle, and we observe a small increase in temperature throughout the sample, with little to zero effective change in the current density profile (Figures 5.11 (e) and (f)).

To note an observable change in the current density profiles due to the temperature rise, the simulation is let to run for up to 150 cycles of applied field. At the end of 50 cycles, we see higher temperatures in the center (in the range of 82 K) in Figure 5.12 (a). The temperature in this region affects the screening currents in the corresponding elements, resulting in lower current densities in this area as compared to the edges (Figure 5.12 (b)). This effect is visible for 150 cycles as well, with higher temperatures and lower current densities at the center (Figures 5.12 (c) and (d)). Since the average temperature reaches a stationary state at around 80 cycles, with very low increase in average temperature between 50 to 80 cycles (Figure 5.9), we do not see much difference in the temperature and current density profiles for 50 and 150 cycles. At higher magnetic field inputs, the underlying mechanics of the screening current penetration and temperature rise stays the same, only the rate of the temperature rise increases.

Thus, we show here that the coupled EM and ET model can accurately take the applied magnetic field as input as well, in addition to the voltage as an input parameter, and is able to explain the underlying mechanics of current and temperature change adequately.

5.2. QUENCH MODELING WITH APPLIED FIELD INPUT

Figure 5.11: Temperature (a,c,g) and current density (b,d,f) profiles for applied field, B_m , of 500 mT, cooling enabled case, at the (a,b) negative peak of first cycle, (c,d) first complete cycle, and (e,f) at the end of the 2nd cycle, respectively.

Figure 5.12: Temperature (a,c) and current density (b,d) profiles for applied field, B_m , of 500 mT, cooling enabled case, at (a) the 50th cycle, and (b) at the 150th cycle, respectively.

5.2. QUENCH MODELING WITH APPLIED FIELD INPUT

Chapter 6

Conclusion

Superconductors can be used in various commercial applications. However, numerically modeling superconductors is a complicated and time-consuming task. We have developed a fast and effective software that can execute multi-physical analysis of superconductors. The software is applied to the problems of cross field demagnetization and electro-thermal quench of superconductors.

Cross field demagnetization of HTS stacks and bulks

Superconducting motors and generators have a high potential to reduce emissions in electric power generation (wind), and mobility (commercial flights and sea transport). The high power density of superconducting motors enable distributed electric or hybrid-electric propulsion in large commercial aircraft, which are more efficient than the present technology. Superconducting stacks or bulks can be used in the rotor of these electric motors. While capable of producing high magnetic fields and current densities, with increasing power per unit weight, one of the major drawback of HTS tapes in the rotor is the cross field demagnetization under the influence of transverse fields, which which can prematurely stop these motors, if not minimized in the motor design.

We show that the 2D Minimum Electro Magnetic Entropy Production (MEMEP) model, using E-J Power Law (called E-J Power Law Model), is able to model the phenomenon of cross field demagnetization of HTS stacks and bulks accurately. The 2D model is satisfactorily bechmarked with 3D model, which in turn is benchmarked with H-formulation and experimental data. We see that the trapped fields at the center of tape lengths of 3 times the width in 3D modeling is practically the same as for the infinitely long tapes in 2D modeling. In many motor designs, such as the radial-flux motor of ASuMED, the stacks are longer than this minimum ratio, and, hence, 2D

modeling is realistic for real applications. We use the 2D MEMEP model to calculate the time constant of the deteriorating curve of the stack's trapped field, a measure of magnetization decay rate, and we see that the numerical results for the time constant also agree with the analytical formulas' results developed by our team.

It is found that the demagnetization of a stack of tapes is dependent on various variables. The time constant increases with tape thickness (when assuming constant J_c), tape width, and number of tapes in stack, and decreases with ripple field amplitude and frequency, and thickness of tape (when assuming constant sheet critical current density, $J_c d$). It is initially seen, from comparing bulks and stacks, that the stacks have higher time constant values, which are calculated for low number of cycles (around 30).

We have also developed a novel effective E-J relation, based on Dynamic Magneto-Resistance (DMR), which we embed in the 2D MEMEP model in place of E-J Power Law (we call this DMR model). The DMR model agrees perfectly with the E-J Power Law model, and it is seen that the DMR model is orders of magnitude faster than the E-J Power Law model (which, in turn, is substantially faster than commercial software) for calculating demagnetization of HTS stacks of tapes. We use DMR model to calculate the demagnetization of a 100-tape stack for over 2 million cycles of ripple field in less than 4 days, which is the current world record. We are also able to model very thin (up to 1 μm) and wide (up to 40 mm) HTS tapes. From this calculation, we see that if the applied ripple field amplitude is below the parallel penetration field of the tape, then the trapped field curves reach an asymptotic value, achieving permanent magnetization for indefinite time. For ripple field amplitudes above the parallel penetration field of the tape, the stack fully demagnetizes. We also compare an interesting case of the same equivalent sized bulks and stacks using DMR model, and we see that for low number of cycles, the stacks demagnetize less. However, for high number of cycles, bulks demagnetize less. This phenomenon is due to the higher parallel penetration fields for bulks, when compared to the same equivalent sized stack, which results in higher range of ripple field amplitudes where bulks can achieve asymptotic field values and retain magnetization indefinitely. Then, regarding cross-field demagnetization, bulks are more convenient than stacks for motors, since the number of ripple field cycles during operation is very high.

Another interesting geometry that we consider is of stacks soldered in pairs to each other face-to-face. For this case, the calculations assume that the tapes are soldered only at the ends, with zero resistance. Our results show that this assumption is valid for realistic values of tape-to-tape resistance when the tapes are soldered face-to-face. A fully soldered stack acts as a bulk, with all the fabrication benefits of stacks, and, thus, it is seen that the soldered stacks have higher parallel penetration fields (double) when compared to the

isolated stacks of equivalent size. From this result, we find that for low number of cycles, isolated stacks demagnetize less, whereas, for high number of cycles, soldered stacks demagnetize less.

The above results are very beneficial for researchers and engineers designing fully superconducting motors for aerospace industry, or any rotating superconducting machine, for quick estimation of their demagnetization rates under the influence of background ripple fields, and we are able to answer essential questions very accurately, such as when the stack will arrive at an asymptotic value and/or the magnitude of this value. For aviation, where we consider using superconducting motors, the ripple field frequencies are in the range of 1000s of Hertz. For the considered frequency in this thesis, 2400 Hz, 2 million cycles of demagnetization calculated by the DMR model corresponds to only about 14 minutes, when the trapped field reaches their asymptotic value for 30 mT. As we saw for the 30 mT ripple field case for the 100-tape stack (Figure 4.31), this will mean that the HTS motors employing this particular stack can lose its power by 53 percent in just under 7 minutes! Thus, the primary goal of the motor designer could be to keep the ripple field amplitude below the parallel penetration field of a tape, and as low as possible, in order to retain as high as possible permanent trapped field. The designer can also use HTS tapes with the highest available critical current per unit tape width (at the operational temperature and background magnetic field).

Coupled Electro-Thermal modeling of superconductors

The developed software in C++ can also perform coupled 2D Electro-Thermal (ET) and Electro-Magnetic (EM) analysis of superconductors. The ET and EM codes interact with each other for each time step, and are based on Minimum Electro-Thermal Entropy Production (METEP) and Minimum Electro-Magnetic Entropy Production (MEMEP), respectively. For modeling the problem of electro-thermal quench, different parameters such as electric voltage and/or applied magnetic field can be used as inputs, both giving rise to currents that heat up the sample by Joule effect.

For applied voltage input, we considered two cases: adiabatic case and cooling enabled case. For high voltages, if the temperature of a sample superconductor rises above its critical temperature (T_c), there is a rapid escalation in the sample's average temperature, which leads to electro-thermal quench. When the studied superconducting bar is immersed in liquid Nitrogen bath, the effective coolant and non-linear nature of superconductors cause that the sample remains superconducting close to the surface, while the interior transits to normal state. For applied magnetic field input, we see that the superconductors can remain superconducting for very high magnetic field amplitudes

without getting quenched (up to 2 T for the considered parameters), when an effective coolant is used.

The software is able to accurately and quickly predict the electro-thermal quench behavior for both applied alternating magnetic field and/or voltage inputs. The software, built using completely new methods, shows great promise for the complete multiphysical analysis of superconductors for different magnet and power applications.

Future Work

Currently, our research team is working on benchmarking cross-field demagnetization in soldered stacks with experiments. We plan to perform coupled Electro-Thermal analysis on the geometry of axisymmetric coil, including temperature dependence of different variables, like $C_v(T)$, $n(T)$, and $k(T)$, and full range of convection coefficient, h , to account for heat transfer to liquid Nitrogen at all temperatures. It is also planned to add a coupled Mechanical formulation, to the Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal models, in the software, which will allow us to completely analyze the multiphysics of superconductors for different commercial and research applications.

Summary

The main highlights of the thesis work are given below.

- A coupled electrothermal software is developed, which performs Electro-Magnetic and Electro-Thermal analysis of superconductors using MEMEP and METEP methods, respectively.
- The 2D MEMEP model is benchmarked, and it can be used for numerically modeling long REBCO tape samples precisely.
- Semi-empirical formulas for time constant are developed and benchmarked.
- Cross field demagnetization of HTS stacks and bulks depends on cross ripple field parameters and sample geometry.
- An effective $E(J)$ relation is developed using Dynamic Magneto-Resistance (DMR model) property of superconductors. DMR model is orders of magnitude faster than conventional models.
- Demagnetization of 100 tape stack for 2 million cycles of applied cross field is numerically calculated in less than 4 days.
- Permanent magnetization is retained in stacks and bulks for ripple field amplitudes below the parallel penetration field of the sample.
- Bulks and soldered stacks demagnetize less than isolated stacks for high number of cycles. For low number of cycles, stacks demagnetize less.
- Electrothermal quench behavior of HTS bulks is successfully modeled utilizing the coupling of MEMEP and METEP methods for different inputs.
- The high rise in temperature and decay of superconducting currents, during the electrothermal quench of superconductors, can be controlled using effective coolants, such as Nitrogen.

Publications and Conferences

Publications

- **Dadhich, A.** and Pardo, E.: Modeling cross-field demagnetization of superconducting stacks and bulks for up to 100 tapes and 2 million cycles, *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), pp.1-11, 19265, 2021. (IF 3.998)
- **Dadhich, A.**, Pardo, E., and Kapolka, M.: Time constant of the transverse-field demagnetization of superconducting stacks of tapes, *Superconductor Science and Technology*, 33(6) 065003, 2020. (IF 3.067)
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- Grilli, F., Benkel, T., Hänisch, J., Lao, M., Reis, T., Berberich, E., Wolfstädter, S., Schneider, C., Miller, P., Palmer, C., Glowacki, B., Climente-Alarcon, V., Smara, A., Tomkow, L., Teigelkötter, J., Stock, A., Büdel, J., Jeunesse, L., Staempflin, M., Delautre, G., Zimmermann, B., van der Woude, R., Perez, A., Samoilenkov, S., Molodyk, A., Pardo, E., Kapolka, M., Li, S., and **Dadhich, A.**: Superconducting motors for aircraft propulsion: the Advanced Superconducting Motor Experimental Demonstrator project, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1590(1) 012051, 2020.

Conferences

Underlined are the presenting authors.

- Dadhich, A., Pardo, E., Solovyov, M. , Li, S., Mosat, M., Souc, J. Reducing cross-field demagnetization in stacks of REBCO tapes by soldering, Materials Research Society (MRS) 2021, Virtual Conference, USA. (Oral)
- Dadhich, A. and Pardo, E.: Modeling the cross field demagnetization of REBCO stacks and bulks for millions of cycles. In Applied Superconductivity Conference (ASC) 2020, Virtual Conference, USA. (Student Paper Competition - Oral)
- Dadhich, A., Kapolka, M., Pardo, E., Climente-Alarcon, V., Smara, A., Mineev, N., Tomkow, L., Glowacki, B.A., and Grilli, F.: Cross-field demagnetization of 2G HTS stacks for high number of cycles. 14th European Conference on Applied Superconductivity (EUCAS) 2019, Glasgow, Scotland. (Oral)
- Pardo, E., Dadhich, A., Li, S., Kapolka, M., Solovyov, M., Mošař, M., Kováč, J., and Šouc, J.: Modeling and measuring the cross field demagnetization of REBCO stacks and bulks for millions of cycles. Applied Superconductivity Conference (ASC) 2020, Virtual Conference, USA. (Invited Talk)
- Grilli, F., Benkel, T., Hänisch, J., Reis, T., Berberich, E., Wolfstädter, S., Schneider, C., Miller, P., Palmer, C., Glowacki, B., Climente-Alarcon, V., Smara, A., Tomkow, L., Teigelkötter, J., Stock, A., Büdel, J., Jennesse, L., Staempflin, M., Delautre, G., Zimmermann, B., van der Woude, R., Perez, A., Samoilenkov, S., Molodyk, A., Pardo, E., Kapolka, M., Li, S., and Dadhich, A.: REBCO coated conductors are ready to take off. SuperFOx 2020, Santa Margherita Ligure, Italy. (Invited Talk)

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